

Ambient Air Temperature Exposure and Foetal Size and Growth in Three European Birth Cohorts

Esmée Essers^{a,b,c,d}, Laura Granés^{a,b,c,e}, Scott Delaney^f, Joan Ballester^a, Susana Santos^{g,h,i,j}, Sami Petricola^{a,b,c}, Tiffany C Yang^k, Ana Fernández-Somoano^{c,l}, Ainhoa Bereziartuaⁿ, Ferran Ballester^{c,o,p}, Adonina Tardón^{c,l,m}, Martine Vrijheid^{a,b,c}, Aitana Lertxundi^{c,m,q}, Rosemary McEachan^k, Hanan El Marroun^{d,r}, Henning Tiemeier^{d,s}, Carmen Iñiguez^{c,t}, Mònica Guxens^{a,b,c,d}

^a ISGlobal, Barcelona, Spain

^b Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

^c Spanish Consortium for Research on Epidemiology and Public Health (CIBERESP), Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Madrid, Spain

^d Department of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry/Psychology, Erasmus MC, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

^e Department of Psychiatry, Bellvitge University Hospital, Bellvitge Biomedical Research Institute-IDIBELL, Barcelona, Spain

^f Department of Environmental Health, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, Boston, USA

^g Generation R Study Group, Erasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam, The Netherlands

^h Department of Pediatrics, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, Rotterdam, the Netherlands

ⁱ EPIUnit - Instituto de Saúde Pública, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal

^j Laboratório para a Investigação Integrativa e Translacional em Saúde Populacional (ITR), Porto, Portugal

^k Bradford Institute for Health Research, Bradford Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, Bradford, UK

^l IUOPA-Department of Medicine, University of Oviedo, Oviedo, Spain

^m Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del Principado de Asturias (ISPA), Oviedo, Spain

ⁿ Health Research Institute, BIODONOSTIA, San Sebastian, Spain

^o Department of Nursing, Universitat de València, Valencia, Spain.

^p Epidemiology and Environmental Health Joint Research Unit, FISABIO- Universitat Jaume I- Universitat de València, Valencia, Spain

^q Department of Preventive Medicine and Public Health, Faculty of Medicine, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain

^r Department of Psychology, Education and Child Studies, Erasmus School of Social and Behavioural Sciences, Erasmus MC, Rotterdam, the Netherlands

^s Department of Social and Behavioral Sciences, Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health, Boston, USA.

^t Department of Statistics and Operational Research, Universitat de València, València, Spain

Correspondence to:

Mònica Guxens, MD, MPH, PhD

Barcelona Institute for Global Health (ISGlobal) – Campus Mar

Carrer Dr. Aiguader 88. 08003-Barcelona, Spain.

E-Mail: monica.guxens@isglobal.org

Keywords:

environmental health, climate change, foetal development, pregnancy, cohort study

1 **Abstract**

2 **Introduction.** Ambient air temperature may affect birth outcomes adversely, but little is known
3 about their impact on foetal growth throughout pregnancy. We evaluated the association
4 between temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size and growth in three European
5 birth cohorts.

6
7 **Methods.** We studied 23,408 pregnant women from the English Born in Bradford cohort, Dutch
8 Generation R Study, and Spanish INMA Project. Using the UrbClim™ model, weekly ambient
9 air temperature exposure at 100x100m resolution at the mothers' residences during pregnancy
10 was calculated. Estimated foetal weight (EFW), head circumference (HC), and femur length
11 (FL) at mid and late pregnancy and weight, HC, and length at birth were converted into standard
12 deviation scores (SDS). Foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy was calculated (grams or
13 centimetres/week). Cohort/region-specific distributed lag non-linear models were combined
14 using a random-effects meta-analysis and results presented in reference to the median percentile
15 of temperature (14°C).

16
17 **Results.** Weekly temperatures ranged from -5.6 (Bradford) to 30.3°C (INMA-Sabadell). Cold
18 and heat exposure during weeks 1-28 were associated with a smaller and larger HC in late
19 pregnancy, respectively (e.g., for 9.5°C: -1.6 SDS [95%CI -2.0; -0.4] and for 20.0°C: 1.8 SDS
20 [0.7; 2.9]). A susceptibility period from weeks 1-7 was identified for cold exposure and a
21 smaller HC at late pregnancy. Cold exposure was associated with a slower HC growth (for
22 5.5°C: -0.1 cm/week [-0.2; -0.04]), with a susceptibility period from weeks 4-12. No
23 associations that survived multiple testing correction were found for other foetal or any birth
24 outcomes.

25
26 **Conclusions.** Cumulative exposure to cold and heat during pregnancy was associated with
27 changes in foetal head circumference throughout gestation, with susceptibility periods for cold
28 during the first pregnancy trimester. No associations were found at birth, suggesting potential
29 recovery. Future research should replicate this study across different climatic regions including
30 varying temperature profiles.

31 **1. Introduction**

32 Global climate change has increased the frequency of extreme temperatures and severe weather
33 events, posing substantial threats to human health and the environment (IPCC, 2022). As the
34 world population grows and urbanization continues, global warming is likely to reach 1.5 °C
35 before 2040 (IPCC, 2022). The World Health Organization and European Environmental
36 Agency warned of irreversible impacts on nature and human health, particularly in Europe
37 where temperature increases are predicted to pass global trends (EEA, 2022; WHO, 2021).

38 Studies showed that exposure to extreme temperatures, both heat and cold, result in a
39 range of health effects, including increased morbidity and mortality (Rocque et al., 2021).
40 Pregnant women and their foetuses are especially vulnerable due to the developmental
41 processes during this lifetime period (Syed et al., 2022; Veenema et al., 2023). The biological
42 mechanism by which temperature influences foetal development remains unclear (Samuels et
43 al., 2022). Studies suggest that sudden changes in temperature may disrupt proper
44 thermoregulation in pregnant women through various mechanisms, including inflammatory
45 responses, oxidative stress, and altered uterine-placental blood flow (Ferguson et al., 2018;
46 Samuels et al., 2022). Rises in ambient air temperature can also trigger the release of heat shock
47 proteins (Ha et al., 2018). Further, exposure to colder temperatures could aggravate
48 beforementioned mechanisms, especially if this co-occurs with an increase in infections with a
49 seasonal pattern (Moriyama et al., 2020). Additionally, seasonal variations have been linked to
50 pregnancy complications like preeclampsia (Liao et al., 2023; Pitakkarnkul et al., 2011). All
51 mechanisms might damage the placenta and contribute to disrupted intrauterine growth
52 (Ferguson et al., 2018; Ha et al., 2018; Samuels et al., 2022).

53 Studies evaluating temperature exposure during pregnancy generally find that exposure
54 to heat or cold is associated with an increased risk of preterm birth or stillbirth, and reduced
55 birth weight (Bakhtsiyarava et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023; de Bont et al., 2022; Giorgis-

56 Allemand et al., 2017; Hough et al., 2022; McElroy et al., 2022; Syed et al., 2022; Yitshak-Sade
57 et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2023). This has been evaluated across various continents and countries
58 with varying temperature profiles (e.g., Latin America, China, Europe, USA). Most studies
59 evaluate the effect of long-term weekly or monthly temperature exposure during entire gestation
60 (Bakhtsiyarava et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023; de Bont et al., 2022; Yitshak-Sade et al., 2021).
61 Associations have also been identified with short-term temperature exposure (i.e., daily
62 temperature exposure prior to the adverse birth outcome) (Hough et al., 2022; McElroy et al.,
63 2022; Yu et al., 2023). However, some studies contradict these findings, showing no
64 associations or even decreased risks (Chen et al., 2023; de Bont et al., 2022; Syed et al., 2022).
65 Researchers have also attempted to identify susceptibility periods for temperature exposure and
66 adverse birth outcomes by employing distributed lag non-linear models (DLNM) (Gasparri, 2014).
67 Identified periods, however, vary in length from weeks to months and in timing across
68 trimesters (Bakhtsiyarava et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023; McElroy et al., 2022; Yitshak-Sade et
69 al., 2021). For cold exposure, one study identified increased susceptibility during the first two
70 months of gestation and another one week before delivery (Chen et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2023).

71 To our knowledge, only one study evaluated the association between temperature
72 exposure and foetal size metrics throughout pregnancy, concluding that higher temperature
73 exposure during pregnancy was associated with smaller head parameters in early- to mid-
74 pregnancy (Leung et al., 2022). During gestation, the foetus undergoes various developmental
75 stages, including the periconceptional and placental formation periods in the initial trimesters,
76 increased adipogenesis in later pregnancy, and brain development throughout gestation
77 (Barbour & Hernandez, 2018; de Graaf-Peters & Hadders-Algra, 2006; Pardi & Cetin, 2006;
78 Steegers-Theunissen et al., 2013). Importantly, various foetal metrics underlie these
79 developmental stages and evaluating them individually is crucial to gain a deeper understanding
80 of changes in foetal development versus focussing solely on endpoint measures like birth weight.

81 Deviations in foetal growth, both restriction and overgrowth, have been associated with
82 increased health risks (Damhuis et al., 2021). While short-term exposure to temperature has
83 been associated with adverse birth outcomes, evaluating foetal development throughout
84 gestation requires a long-term exposure approach to capture any possible deviations.
85 Investigating how and when long-term temperature exposure influences developmental periods
86 during pregnancy is crucial, as varying long-term consequences might arise (Pardi & Cetin,
87 2006). Our main aim is to evaluate the association between ambient air temperature exposure
88 across pregnancy and foetal size and growth in three European birth cohorts. Our secondary
89 aim is to identify specific periods of susceptibility to air temperature exposure throughout
90 pregnancy.

91

92 **2. Methods**

93 **2.1 Population and Study Design**

94 This study is embedded in three population-based birth cohort studies, namely the English Born
95 in Bradford Study, the Dutch Generation R Study, and the Spanish INfancia y Medio Ambiente
96 Project (INMA). Born in Bradford recruited 12,453 pregnant women living in the city of
97 Bradford, the United Kingdom, between 2007 and 2011, who were planning to deliver at the
98 city's main maternity unit (Wright et al., 2013). Generation R recruited 8,879 pregnant women
99 living in Rotterdam, the Netherlands, who were expected to deliver between April 2002 and
100 January 2006 (Kooijman et al., 2016). INMA recruited pregnant women living in several
101 regions of Spain between 1997 and 2008 (Guxens et al., 2012). The current study includes
102 women from four regions, namely Asturias (N=494), Gipuzkoa (N=638), Sabadell (N=657),
103 and Valencia (N=827), who were recruited between 2003 and 2008. We included women with
104 live singleton births, complete temperature data during weeks 1 – 32 of pregnancy, and at least
105 one outcome measure available, resulting in a total sample size of 23,408 participants (Figure

106 S1). The 32-week threshold was selected to ensure losing less than 5% of the population while
107 only excluding extremely and very preterm births. Prior to recruitment, ethical approval was
108 obtained for Born in Bradford (Bradford Leeds NHS Research Ethics Committee), Generation
109 R (Medical Ethical Committee of Erasmus University Medical Centre Rotterdam, in accordance
110 with Dutch law), and INMA (Ethical Committee of the Municipal Institute of Medical
111 Investigation and the Ethical Committee of the hospitals involved in the study). Informed
112 consent was obtained from participants.

113

114 **2.2 Temperature Exposure**

115 Assessment of ambient air temperature exposure was done using the urban climate model
116 UrbClimTM (De Ridder et al., 2015). The model uses a 3D atmospheric boundary layer module
117 coupled with urban physics and includes information on the urban structure. The model has
118 been validated in various European countries, and more detailed methodology is described in
119 Methods S1 and elsewhere (De Ridder et al., 2015; Garcíá-Diéz et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al.,
120 2015, 2016). Hourly 2-meter air temperature (°C) was estimated at a high spatial resolution of
121 100 x 100 metres (Figure S2) and converted into daily data. The daily data were assigned to the
122 geocoded address where the mother lived on that day, thereby accounting any changes in
123 address. Daily data started on the date of the last menstrual period. The last menstrual period in
124 the Born in Bradford cohort was determined by subtracting 14 days from the conception date,
125 the latter determined by subtracting the estimated gestational age at the ultrasound examination
126 from the date of birth, in Generation R it was obtained from the referral letter and questionnaires
127 and confirmed at enrolment and in INMA it was reported at recruitment and confirmed during
128 the first ultrasound examination. If the last menstrual period was missing (2.4% of all
129 participants with temperature data in Born in Bradford, 0.9% in Generation R, and 0.0% in
130 INMA), it was estimated by subtracting 280 days from the date of birth. If the first-known

131 address was recorded after the date of the last menstrual period (12.9% of all participants in
132 Born in Bradford, 15.3% in Generation R, and 1.6% for INMA), we assumed this address to be
133 representative for the address since the date of the last menstrual period and used it for all
134 following days until a next address was recorded. Mean temperatures for each week of
135 pregnancy (i.e., seven consecutive days from the date of the last menstrual period until the 7th
136 day of the 32nd week of pregnancy) were calculated by averaging the daily data.

137 We validated the daily UrbClimTM temperature with the data of measuring stations from
138 E-OBS (daily gridded observational data for temperature in Europe (Cornes et al., 2018)). The
139 performance was very good and showed a multiple R² of 0.97, 0.89, and 0.95 and a root mean
140 squared error of 1.20, 1.71, and 1.57 °C for Generation R, Born in Bradford, and INMA,
141 respectively.

142

143 **2.3 Foetal Assessment**

144 *2.3.1 Foetal size at mid and late pregnancy*

145 During pregnancy, ultrasound examinations were carried out by trained sonographers, and
146 foetal size measurements were collected following specific guidelines within each cohort
147 (Iñiguez et al., 2016; Kirwan, 2010; Verburg et al., 2008). The examinations at mid pregnancy
148 took place during the second trimester of pregnancy (at an average of 20.4 weeks of gestation
149 for Born in Bradford, and 20.6 for Generation R and INMA) and at late pregnancy during the
150 third trimester (at an average of 32.8 weeks of gestation for Born in Bradford, 30.5 for
151 Generation R, and 33.3 for INMA) (Table S1). During the ultrasound examinations, head
152 circumference and femur length were measured in centimetres (cm). The estimated foetal
153 weight (EFW) in grams (g) was calculated using the Hadlock formula IV, with abdominal
154 circumference (AC), femur length (FL), head circumference (HC), and biparietal diameter
155 (BPD) as input variables (Hadlock et al., 1985; Hammami et al., 2018):

156
$$\text{Log}_{10} (EFW) = 1.3596 - 0.00386 * AC * FL + 0.0064 * HC +$$

157
$$0.0061 * BPD * AC + 0.0424 * AC + 0.174 * FL$$

158 Raw measurements of estimated foetal weight, head circumference, and femur length were
159 harmonized across cohorts by converting them into gestational age- and sex-adjusted standard
160 deviation scores (SDS) based on European reference growth curves from the World Health
161 Organization (Kiserud et al., 2017).

162

163 **2.3.2 Foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy**

164 Foetal growth was defined as the absolute change in foetal size from mid to late pregnancy. It
165 was calculated for estimated foetal weight (g/week), head circumference (cm/week), and femur
166 length (cm/week) by determining the difference between the foetal size measure at late and mid
167 pregnancy divided by the difference in gestational age between late and mid pregnancy.

168

169 **2.4 Birth Outcomes Assessment**

170 Measurements at birth were collected from medical records within each cohort (Iñiguez et al.,
171 2016; Kirwan, 2010; Verburg et al., 2008). Birth weight (g), head circumference at birth (cm),
172 and birth length (cm) were assessed. The raw measurements of birth weight, head circumference
173 at birth, and birth length were converted into gestational age- and sex-adjusted SDS using
174 growth reference charts specific to each cohort (Freeman et al., 1995; Gurrin et al., 2001;
175 Niklasson et al., 1991; Pinheiro & Bates, 2000). For Born in Bradford, SDS of head
176 circumference at birth were not available and birth length data was not collected.

177

178 **2.5 Potential Confounding Variables**

179 Potential confounding variables for all cohorts were determined a priori using a directed acyclic
180 graph based on previous scientific literature, biological plausibility, and available data (Figure

181 S3). We harmonized the variables across cohorts. We included information on maternal age
182 (years), national/ethnic origin (White British, South Asian, or Other in Born in Bradford; the
183 Netherlands, Morocco, Suriname/Dutch Antilles, Turkey, or Other in Generation R; and Spain
184 or Other in INMA), family status (couple or single parent), parity (nulliparous, one child, two
185 or more children), maternal smoking use (never in pregnancy, until pregnancy known,
186 continued), maternal alcohol use (never in pregnancy, until pregnancy known, occasionally,
187 frequent), and maternal and paternal education level (low, medium, high). Maternal height (cm)
188 and pre-pregnancy weight (kg) were measured or self-reported in the first trimester of
189 pregnancy and subsequently used to calculate body mass index (BMI, kg/m²). Exposure to
190 surrounding greenness at the residential address during pregnancy in a buffer of 300 meters was
191 determined using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (considering changes of address).
192 The value was determined using satellite data estimating the degree of absorbance of red light
193 of vegetation, and the index ranges from -1 to 1, with a higher value indicating more greenness
194 (Rhew et al., 2011). We adjusted the models for seasonality by including month of conception.
195 We additionally adjusted for foetal sex (female or male) in foetal growth analyses. We did not
196 adjust for air pollution exposure because temperature is involved in the formation and therefore
197 quantity of air pollutants (Buckley et al., 2014; Reid et al., 2012), making air pollution a
198 mediator on the causal pathway between temperature and health outcomes (Jakpor et al., 2020)
199 (Figure S3).

200

201 **2.6 Statistical Analyses**

202 Missing values of potential confounding variables were imputed following the procedure for
203 expectation-maximization imputation using the ‘Amelia’ R package v1.8.0 (Honaker et al.,
204 2012). Imputation was performed independently in each cohort/region including subjects that
205 have available data on temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 32 of pregnancy and at least one

206 outcome available (Table S2). For all potential confounding variables, the percentage of missing
207 values was below 30%, except paternal educational level in Born in Bradford and Generation
208 R (38.4% and 39.6%, respectively). Imputed and observed datasets showed comparable
209 distributions for each cohort (Table S3).

210 Within each cohort, mothers that were included in the analyses had some different
211 characteristics compared to those excluded (Table S4). We performed inverse probability
212 weighting in the full sample of each cohort/region separately, to correct for selection bias and
213 prevent underrepresentation of characteristics in the study sample (Weisskopf et al., 2015). We
214 used a generalized linear model that includes determinants of participation (list of variables
215 used can be found in Table S4) to predict the marginal probability of participation in the current
216 study. The final weight per subject was calculated as the inverse of the probability and used as
217 weights in all DLNM. The distribution of the weights in each cohort/region can be found in
218 Figure S4.

219 To evaluate the delayed association between ambient air temperature exposure during
220 pregnancy and each outcome, we used DLNM (Gasparrini, 2014; Gasparrini et al., 2010). These
221 models estimate the exposure-response relationship while simultaneously accounting for the
222 delayed associations between exposure and response (lag-response relationship), considering
223 the correlation within the time-series data. The interval of time between the delayed effect of
224 the exposure and the outcome is defined as the lag scale and can be divided into equally spaced
225 time periods. Some model specifications were set based on visual inspection of the data,
226 previous literature, and biological plausibility. First, we harmonized the exposure period for all
227 participants, since the exposure matrix does not allow for missing lags. We established weekly
228 exposure windows that started from the first week of gestation and ended prior to each
229 outcome's assessment. We selected the longest possible threshold while ensuring maximum
230 sample size after evaluating possible window thresholds between the minimum (14.1 weeks for

231 mid and 28.1 for late pregnancy) and the mean (20.5 weeks for mid and 31.8 for late pregnancy)
232 of gestational age in the analysis sample of 23,408. This meant that we included 18 one-week
233 lags for outcomes at mid pregnancy or growth from mid to late pregnancy and 28 one-week
234 lags for outcomes at late pregnancy. For birth outcomes we included the threshold of 32 one-
235 week lags following the same procedure. Second, we defined the functions of the DLNM cross-
236 basis (dimensional space of two functions describing the exposure-response and lag-response
237 relationships). We used generalised additive models to explore the linearity of the dose-
238 response relationship between each week of exposure and each outcome. After visual inspection,
239 we observed that all relationships were non-linear. We therefore modelled the exposure-
240 response relationship using natural cubic splines with knots at the 25th and 75th percentile of
241 temperature exposure distribution for the relevant lag periods. For the lag-response relationship,
242 we selected natural cubic splines and added one knot centred over the full lag period of each
243 outcome.

244 Our main analysis followed a two-stage approach: we performed cohort/region-specific
245 DLNMs for each outcome and then a meta-analysis. In the first stage, we evaluated the
246 cumulative association between ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and i)
247 foetal *size* (at mid and at late pregnancy), ii) foetal *growth* from mid to late pregnancy, and iii)
248 birth outcomes. The cumulative association represents the combined effect of exposure to
249 temperature throughout the entire lag period on the outcome of interest. To avoid the influence
250 of extreme percentiles, for each cohort/region-specific DLNM, we determined the estimated
251 coefficients for the 1st to 99th temperature percentiles based on the exposure matrix for the lag-
252 period and cohort/region of interest. Models were adjusted for all beforementioned potential
253 confounding variables. We set the centring value (reference temperature) to the 50th percentile
254 of the cohort/region-specific temperature distribution respective to each lag period.

255 In the second stage, we combined the estimated coefficients from the cohort/region-
256 specific DLNM using a random effects meta-analysis including a random effect by
257 cohort/region. To reduce heterogeneity when present, we tested the inclusion of temperature
258 characteristics of the three climatic regions representing our study population as fixed effects.
259 These three climatic regions were the following: i) subtropical maritime (INMA-Asturias and
260 INMA-Gipuzkoa), ii) subtropical continental (INMA-Sabadell and INMA-Valencia), and iii)
261 temperate maritime (Born in Bradford and Generation R) (European Environmental Agency,
262 2012). The temperature characteristics of each climatic region (i.e., range of temperature and
263 average temperature) were tested in models including all possible combinations (either one or
264 the other or both of them). We chose the model that showed a lower I^2 statistic and significant
265 Wald test ($p < 0.05$) for the selected fixed effect variables. As a result of these analyses, the
266 range of temperature was included in models evaluating head circumference at late pregnancy;
267 the average temperature was included in models evaluating head circumference at mid and
268 femur length at late pregnancy; both characteristics were included in models evaluating
269 estimated foetal weight at mid pregnancy and head circumference growth and femur length
270 growth from mid to late pregnancy; and no temperature characteristics were included for all
271 other outcomes. Random-effects meta-analysis were fitted through restricted maximum
272 likelihood. The final global estimates were plotted as dose-response curves including the
273 confidence intervals that show the cumulative association between ambient air temperature
274 exposure during pregnancy and each outcome centred at the 50th percentile of temperature
275 distribution averaged across all cohorts (14 °C). Following the approach by Galwey, we
276 corrected for multiple testing on the outcome by determining the eigenvalues to identify the
277 effective number of tests using the ‘poolr’ package and ‘meff’ function in R (Galwey, 2009).
278 The effective number of tests was six for the foetal analyses (three exposure periods and three
279 foetal outcomes = nine effective outcomes) and two for the birth outcomes analyses (one

280 exposure period and the three birth outcomes = three effective outcomes) making the new
281 statistical significance level $0.05/6=0.0083$ for foetal analyses, and $0.05/2=0.025$ for the birth
282 outcomes analyses. Associations that remained statistically significant after correction for
283 multiple testing were highlighted in the final plots.

284 As a secondary analysis, we attempted to identify susceptibility periods during
285 pregnancy if any meta-analysed dose-response curve obtained from the second stage showed
286 statistically significant associations after multiple testing correction. We used the cohort/region-
287 specific DLNM to estimate the coefficients for each pregnancy week when exposed to specific
288 predictors for cold (2.5th percentile of temperature) or heat (97.5th percentile of temperature)
289 (Table S6), depending on the statistically significant associations found in the main analysis.
290 The centring value was set to the 50th percentile of the cohort/region-specific temperature
291 distributions. The same meta-analysis approach as the second stage of the main analysis was
292 then used. Final global estimates were plotted as lag-response curves including the confidence
293 intervals, that show the association between ambient air temperature exposure at the selected
294 predictor for cold (2.5th versus 50th percentile) or heat (97.5th versus 50th percentile) for each
295 week of pregnancy and the outcome. The final centring value was set to the 50th percentile of
296 the temperature distribution averaged across all cohorts respective to each full exposure period
297 (averaged to 14 °C, Table S6).

298 To evaluate the robustness of our results, we performed sensitivity analyses and tested
299 different DLNM specifications: i) we set the knots in the exposure-response relationship at the
300 10th and 90th percentile of temperature distribution; ii) we modelled the lag-response
301 relationship linearly and with two equally distributed knots in the lag period; iii) we excluded
302 children born moderate to late preterm by only including mothers that have temperature
303 exposure during weeks 1 to 38 of pregnancy and used a lag period of 38 instead of 32 weeks
304 for birth outcomes; iv) we evaluated the associations for birth outcomes using a lag period of

305 18 or 28 weeks to compare with the results of foetal size and foetal growth outcomes; v) we
306 stratified the main analysis by foetal sex; vi) we included only mothers with a national origin
307 from the respective cohort; vii) we stratified by cohort/region for the outcomes in which an
308 overall association was found; viii) we evaluated all associations excluding the Born in
309 Bradford cohort; and finally, ix) we evaluated associations for the foetal outcomes including
310 only mothers with available data at mid and late pregnancy for each foetal metric.

311 All analyses were done using R version 4.0.3 [R Core Team 2020], the DLNM and
312 meta-analyses were conducted using the ‘dlnm’ and ‘mixmeta’ packages, respectively.

313

314 **3. Results**

315 **3.1 Population Characteristics**

316 Table 1 shows all population characteristics. The average age of mothers varied between 27.4
317 and 31.5 years across the cohorts. Parents from Generation R were more highly educated (42.3%
318 of mothers and 50.9% of fathers), while parents from INMA mostly had a medium education
319 level (average of 41.4% of mothers and 44.2% of fathers across regions), and those from Born
320 in Bradford a low education level (56.8% of mothers and 53.0% of fathers). Between 11.5%
321 and 22.8% of mothers continued to smoke during pregnancy across cohorts. The temporal
322 pattern for weekly ambient air temperature in the 30x30 km temperature domain for each
323 cohort/region throughout the years of pregnancy is shown in Figure 1. During pregnancy weeks
324 1 to 32, Born in Bradford had mothers who experienced the coldest average weekly
325 temperatures (minimum -5.6 °C) and INMA-Sabadell the hottest (maximum 30.3 °C). From
326 mid to late pregnancy, estimated foetal weight growth ranged from 125.9 (Standard Deviation,
327 SD 18.3) g/week in Generation R to 151.7 (SD 18.4) in INMA-Sabadell; head circumference
328 growth ranged from 0.9 in INMA-Gipuzkoa and INMA-Sabadell to 1.1 (SD 0.1) cm/week in
329 Generation R; and femur length growth was 0.2 (SD 0.02) cm/week for all cohorts (Table S7).

Table 1. Population characteristics of the three European birth cohorts.

	Born in	Generation	INMA			
	Bradford (N = 12,701)	R (N = 8,319)	Asturias (N = 469)	Gipuzkoa (N = 599)	Sabadell (N = 611)	Valencia (N = 709)
<i>Child Characteristics</i>						
Sex (female vs. male)	48.5	49.6	48.0	49.6	49.6	47.2
Season of conception						
Summer	26.2	23.7	21.3	30.2	28.6	22.7
Fall	25.9	27.4	28.6	23.0	23.4	20.7
Winter	25.2	26.7	26.2	16.7	21.0	31.6
Spring	26.2	22.2	23.9	30.0	27.0	25.0
Gestational age at birth (weeks)	39.6 (1.7)	39.9 (1.6)	39.5 (1.4)	39.8 (1.4)	39.7 (1.4)	39.7 (1.5)
Birth weight (grams)	3207 (574)	3243 (540)	3275 (459)	3301 (448)	3246 (425)	3255 (488)
Head circumference at birth (cm)	na ¹	33.8 (1.7)	34.2 (1.4)	34.8 (1.4)	34.2 (1.2)	34.1 (1.5)
Birth length (cm)	na	50.2 (2.4)	49.7 (2.0)	49.0 (1.9)	49.4 (1.9)	50.2 (2.1)
<i>Maternal Characteristics</i>						
Age (years)	27.4 (5.6)	29.7 (5.3)	31.5 (4.4)	31.4 (3.6)	30.2 (4.4)	29.8 (4.5)
Pre-pregnancy body mass index (kg/m ²)	26.0 (5.7)	23.6 (4.3)	23.8 (4.3)	22.9 (3.6)	23.7 (4.5)	23.8 (4.7)
Education level						
High	27.6	42.3	36.5	51.1	29.0	23.4
Medium	15.6	30.8	44.8	35.7	43.0	42.2
Low	56.8	26.9	18.8	13.2	28.0	34.4
National/ethnic origin						
Country of cohort	41.1	49.6	96.4	95.8	89.0	88.2
South Asian	54.0	na	na	na	na	na
Morocco	na	6.9	na	na	na	na
Suriname / Dutch Antilles	na	12.3	na	na	na	na
Turkey	na	9.4	na	na	na	na
Other	5.0	21.7	3.6	4.2	11.0	11.8
Alcohol use during pregnancy						
Never	80.2	47.6	89.1	82.2	77.9	74.5
Until pregnancy known	6.7	12.9	5.3	6.0	5.7	7.8
Occasionally	9.5	32.0	5.5	11.8	16.4	17.8
Frequent	3.6	7.4	na	na	na	na
Smoking during pregnancy						
Never	83.7	72.9	71.4	76.3	69.7	59.0
Until pregnancy known	2.9	8.6	11.0	12.2	16.0	18.2
Continued	13.4	18.5	17.6	11.5	14.3	22.8
Parity						
0 children	39.3	55.5	61.0	53.8	56.5	55.0
1 child	29.0	30.0	33.9	40.1	37.1	36.4
2+ children	31.7	14.5	5.1	6.2	6.4	8.6
Family status (couple vs. single parent)	83.9	85.6	98.1	99.3	98.8	97.6
<i>Paternal Characteristics</i>						
Education level						
High	33.4	50.9	22.8	26.3	21.2	14.9
Medium	13.7	26.4	46.2	49.1	43.5	38.2
Low	53.0	22.6	31.0	24.6	35.4	46.9
<i>Residential Characteristics</i>						
Surrounding greenness	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)

Values are percentage for categorical and mean (standard deviation) for continuous variables. Na: not available. ¹ Head circumference at birth was available as absolute values (centimetres) in the Born in Bradford cohort, but since the standard deviation score was not available, this metric was not used in the current manuscript and therefore not shown in the table.

Figure 1. Average weekly ambient air temperature in °C during the years of pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts.

331

332 **3.2 Foetal size at mid and late pregnancy**

333 Results from the meta-analysis for the foetal size measures show that after correction for
334 multiple testing, cumulative exposure to colder or hotter temperatures in the central range of
335 temperature from conception to week 28 of pregnancy was associated with a smaller and larger
336 head circumference in late pregnancy, respectively (e.g., exposure to 9.5 °C (vs. 14.0 °C) was
337 associated with -1.61 SDS of head circumference [95% Confidence Interval, CI -2.81; -0.42]
338 and exposure to 20 °C (vs. 14.0 °C) was associated with 1.78 larger SDS of head circumference
339 [95% CI 0.66; 2.85]) (Figure 2B and Table S8). A susceptible period for exposure to cold (2.5th
340 percentile or 4.2 °C) was found between weeks 1 and 7 for a smaller head circumference at late
341 pregnancy (cumulative effect estimate of -0.1 SDS), but not for exposure to heat (Figure 3A
342 and Table S9). Results further show associations for exposure to hotter temperatures and a
343 larger head circumference but smaller femur length at mid pregnancy (Figure 2A) and for
344 exposure to colder temperatures and a smaller femur length at late pregnancy (Figure 2B),
345 although these associations did not survive correction for multiple testing. No associations for
346 estimated foetal weight at mid or late pregnancy were found (Figure 2).

347

348 **3.3 Foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy**

349 Results from the meta-analysis for the foetal growth outcomes show that cumulative exposure
350 to colder temperatures between 5.5 and 7.0 °C (vs. 14.0 °C) from conception to week 18 of
351 pregnancy was associated with a slower head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy
352 (e.g., exposure to 5.5 °C was associated with -0.1 cm/week of head circumference [95% CI -
353 0.2; -0.04] (Figure 2C and Table S10). A susceptibility period for exposure to cold (2.5th
354 percentile or 4.2 °C) was found between weeks 4 and 12 for a slower head circumference growth
355 from mid to late pregnancy (cumulative effect estimate of -0.01 centimetres) (Figure 3B and
356 Table S11). Results further show associations for exposure to colder temperatures and a slower

357 estimated foetal weight and femur length growth from mid to late pregnancy and to hotter
358 temperatures and a faster femur length growth from mid to late pregnancy, although these
359 associations did not survive correction for multiple testing (Figure 2C).

360

361 **3.4 Birth Outcomes**

362 We found no statistically significant evidence of associations between cumulative temperature
363 exposure from conception to week 32 of pregnancy and birth weight (Figure 4 and Table S12)
364 or head circumference at birth or birth length (Figure S5 and Table S12).

365

366 **3.5 Sensitivity Analyses**

367 When adjusting the DLNM specifications by changing the knot placements in the exposure-
368 response relationship or evaluating the lag-response relationship linearly or with two knots,
369 results from the meta-analysis for all outcomes showed similar global curves (Figures S6, S7
370 and S8). Further, limiting the sample size to mothers with temperature data during weeks 1 to
371 38 of pregnancy showed comparable results (Figure S9). Adjusting the lag period to 18 or 28
372 weeks for all birth outcomes also showed similar curves to the main analysis (Figure S10).
373 When stratifying the main analysis for foetal sex, results for head circumference at late
374 pregnancy were observed for both girls and boys, but the effects of cold on head circumference
375 growth were only seen in boys and not girls (Figure S11). Restricting the population to only
376 mothers with a national origin of their respective cohorts showed comparable plots as the main
377 analysis (Figure S12). Cohort/region-specific plots for head circumference at late pregnancy
378 and growth from mid to late pregnancy suggested that the overall association was mainly driven
379 by the INMA-Asturias cohort (Figures S13 and S14). Finally, both excluding the Born in
380 Bradford cohort from analyses or restricting the population to only mothers with available foetal
381 data at both mid and late pregnancy revealed similar curves (Figures S15 and S16).

Figure 2. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, and foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C) in the three European birth cohorts.

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C) or 1 to 28 (B) of pregnancy. The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature (14 °C). Blue or red shaded areas (exposure to colder and hotter temperatures, respectively, as compared to 14 °C) indicate statistically significant associations after correction for multiple testing (p-value < 0.0083). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure 3. Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure to cold (blue) or heat (red) during each week of pregnancy and (A) head circumference at late pregnancy or (B) head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy.

Dots represent the global estimate of the association between the exposure to the respective percentile at each lag and the foetal outcome with the 95% confidence intervals as vertical lines obtained from random-effect meta-analysis. Blue or red dots and vertical lines indicate exposure to the 2.5th and 97.5th percentile of temperature exposure within each cohort, respectively, centred to the 50th percentile (14 °C). Yellow shaded areas indicate associations that were statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education level, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure 4. Adjusted association between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure levels (°C) during pregnancy and birth weight in the three European birth cohorts (N = 22,950).

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 32 of pregnancy. The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature (14 °C). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

385

386 **4. Discussion**

387 In this study using data from three birth cohorts in Europe, we found that cumulative
 388 exposure to colder and hotter temperatures was associated with changes in head
 389 circumference size and growth during gestation. Susceptibility periods for exposure to
 390 cold were identified during pregnancy weeks 1 to 7 for a smaller head circumference at
 391 late pregnancy and weeks 4 to 12 for a slower head circumference growth. Although
 392 associations were identified for other foetal metrics, these did not survive multiple testing
 393 correction. No evidence of associations was found between temperature exposure and
 394 birth outcomes.

395 Exposure to hot temperatures can lead to heat stress in pregnant woman, initiating
396 processes that might damage placental growth and consequently contribute to disrupted
397 foetal growth (Ferguson et al., 2018; Ha et al., 2018; Samuels et al., 2022). Animal and
398 human studies have elucidated that maternal heat stress can prompt vasodilation,
399 redistributing blood flow away from the uterine and placental regions towards the skin,
400 disrupt nutrient exchange and deprive the foetus of oxygen, all at the expense of critical
401 placental and foetal organ development (Cowell et al., 2023; Herrick & Bordoni, 2023;
402 Wang & Zhao, 2010). We observed a larger head circumference at late pregnancy with
403 exposure to warmer temperatures, but found no susceptible periods. Head circumference
404 serves as an indicator for head growth, a process intertwined with many brain
405 developmental processes, particularly during early and mid-pregnancy (Gale et al., 2004,
406 2006; Thompson & Nelson, 2001). To our knowledge, only one study evaluated
407 temperature exposure and head circumference size throughout pregnancy and found
408 results contradictory to ours in which higher temperatures from conception to week 20 of
409 pregnancy were associated with a smaller head circumference at mid or late pregnancy
410 (Leung et al., 2022). Further, in contrast to most literature, we found no evidence of
411 associations between hotter temperatures and birth weight, even when considering
412 different exposure periods. Studies have found associations between heat and a lower
413 birth weight, with variable susceptibility periods ranging from weeks during the first
414 trimester to the final months of pregnancy, or across the entire gestational period
415 (Bakhtsiyarava et al., 2022; Basagaña et al., 2021; Leung et al., 2022; Yitshak-Sade et al.,
416 2021). The inconsistency in susceptibility periods could be due to the varying exposure
417 windows (months versus weeks) or the location-specific differences in climate (Latin
418 America, Israel, and Massachusetts, USA), highlighting also why we might not be finding
419 any associations.

420 Cold temperature exposure can result in increased blood viscosity and
421 vasoconstriction, elevating blood pressure in pregnant women (Kimura et al., 1998; Sun
422 et al., 2023; Usselman et al., 2015). Changes in uterine-placental blood flow, similar to
423 heat exposure, can disrupt development of vital foetal organs, including the brain (Herrick
424 & Bordoni, 2023; Wang & Zhao, 2010). This might explain why we see a smaller head
425 circumference at late pregnancy and a slower head circumference growth from mid to late
426 pregnancy for exposure to colder temperatures. These associations were mainly due to
427 susceptibility periods to temperature exposure during the first trimester of pregnancy.
428 From the first until the second trimester, foetal brain development is characterized by
429 neurogenesis and gliogenesis, processes integral for proper formation and functioning of
430 the central nervous system (Leibovitz et al., 2022). Our results suggest that exposure to
431 cold could potentially disrupt crucial brain developmental processes. Further, the
432 identified seven- and nine-week susceptible periods for exposure to cold during the first
433 trimester, align with susceptible periods found by Leung *et al.* for exposure to heat (Leung
434 et al., 2022). Our results for exposure to colder and hotter temperatures and the
435 associations found by Leung and colleagues, might suggest that head circumference size
436 and growth throughout gestation could be influenced by both hot and cold temperatures
437 (Leung et al., 2022). Finally, associations of exposure to temperature and head
438 circumference at late pregnancy were identifiable in both male and female foetuses, while
439 associations for exposure to cold with a slower head circumference growth were only
440 seen in male foetuses. To the best of our knowledge, only one study has explored sex-
441 related differences in vulnerability to temperature exposure and foetal metrics during
442 gestation, and found increased vulnerability for female foetuses (Leung et al., 2022).
443 However, the exact mechanisms are still unknown and further research is needed in
444 understanding whether our results are confirmed or due to chance finding.

445 Overall, even though we found associations of exposure to heat and cold with
446 measurements of foetal growth across pregnancy, no associations were found with the
447 corresponding birth outcomes, suggesting that the effects seen throughout gestation might
448 recover at birth. Also, our results might be due to chance finding, even though we applied
449 correction for multiple testing. It is worth noting that the magnitude of the identified
450 associations was small and that the results for head circumference at late pregnancy only
451 indicated associations in the central range of temperature while we were expecting
452 stronger results on the temperature extremes. Furthermore, the duration of the identified
453 susceptible periods during the first trimester of pregnancy are relatively short within the
454 broader context of pregnancy and might not translate into clinically significant effects.
455 Nevertheless, the changes we observed in foetal size and growth could represent transient
456 effects experienced by relatively short periods of exposure to relatively moderate cold or
457 hot temperatures that are not constant across the entire pregnancy. Even though the
458 magnitude and duration might limit the practical significance of the results, these effects
459 might be further aggravated by climate change if exposure periods to cold or hot
460 temperatures become more extreme and longer.

461 Our study has several important strengths. Firstly, we were able to include a large
462 sample size from different population-based birth cohort studies based in countries with
463 varying climates, increasing our external validity, and making the results from our multi-
464 site study more robust. Aside from capturing the climate variability, our population was
465 ethnically diverse with detailed data on socio-economic and lifestyle characteristics. We
466 were able to adjust for some maternal behaviours during pregnancy that might contribute
467 to foetal growth restriction. Further, we employed inverse probability weighting to limit
468 selection bias and ensure representative results of the initial study population. Second, we
469 had temperature data with a high temporal and spatial resolution, which minimizes

470 exposure misclassification and more precisely accounts for the temporal and spatial
471 variation. Considering the between-subject variability in exposure properly helps mitigate
472 bias in our effect estimates. Third, we used an appropriate model for the delayed
473 relationship between our exposure and response, ensuring the maximum amount of data
474 was used for analyses. DLNMs minimizes confounding by seasonality by mutually
475 adjusting for the temperature exposure in other pregnancy weeks and avoiding multiple
476 comparisons for the exposure. Also, modelling the lag-exposure-response relationship
477 non-linearly ensures that trends associated with both cold and hot temperatures are
478 adequately captured. Lastly, the DLNM approach allows for evaluation of possible
479 susceptible periods throughout gestation, aiding a deeper understanding of which foetal
480 developmental phases might be more affected.

481 However, our study also encompasses some limitations related to the exposure
482 and outcome assessments, and to the study design that merit discussion. With regards to
483 the temperature assessment, we must consider the possibility of measurement error of the
484 exposure and subsequent exposure misclassification. We have collected information on
485 outdoor residential values but were not able to account for factors that may modify the
486 individual levels of exposure (e.g., air conditioning or heating use, behavioural and
487 activity patterns). Additionally, we were unable to account for temperature
488 acclimatization, a process that occurs when individuals are repeatedly exposed to extreme
489 temperatures over a multi-day period, potentially diminishing the effects we observe as it
490 influences physiological responses and makes an individual more capable of handling
491 extreme exposure (Soulтанakis-Aligianni, 2003). For example, populations that
492 experience hotter temperatures, INMA-Sabadell and -Valencia, are more likely to be
493 acclimatized to these temperatures and have a higher preparedness with regards to heat.
494 Lastly, although ambient air temperature is a widely used measure of temperature that

495 can capture the direct effects on health outcomes, future studies should aim to incorporate
496 other health-related measures of temperature, such as apparent temperature or the urban
497 heat island index to evaluate the complexity of combined effects with other atmospheric
498 factors. We chose not to incorporate the former in the current study due to its high
499 correlation with ambient air temperature (0.99) in our sample. With regards to the
500 outcome assessment, we need to consider the possibility of live-birth bias. We might
501 conclude that the effect of temperature exposure on the foetal and birth metrics is less
502 harmful because we are excluding information from those foetuses that are more
503 susceptible (i.e., excluding extremely and very preterm children and miscarriages). We
504 were also unable to calculate foetal growth from mid or late pregnancy to birth because
505 the foetal size metrics were not directly comparable to the metrics at birth. Finally, while
506 the reference growth curves utilized to compute standard deviation scores for foetal size
507 outcomes are based on expansive, representative datasets for foetal growth patterns from
508 the World Health Organization, discernible disparities between cohort/regions – such as
509 genetic variations or healthcare access – underscore the potential limitations in accurately
510 representing each cohort/region to an equal degree. With regards to our statistical analysis,
511 even though DLNMs are powerful tools to evaluate time-series data, they have some
512 limitations. First, many model decisions are made a priori and do not follow specific
513 guidelines. The model can be sensitive to parameter changes, and results should therefore
514 be interpreted with caution; however, our sensitivity analyses testing different parameters
515 showed comparable results to the main analysis. Also, an artefact of the cubic constraint
516 of the DLNM is the over-smoothing of associations, assuming that the exposure-response
517 relationship varies smoothly over the lagged exposures (Mork & Wilson, 2022). Lastly,
518 the DLNM requires the exposure history of a participant to contain no missing values,
519 meaning that we could be missing important weeks of exposure closer to the outcome

520 assessment or at the end of gestation. However, selected thresholds at mid and late
521 pregnancy were close to the means of the gestational ages of the sample and our
522 sensitivity analyses in participants with exposure during weeks 1 to 38 showed
523 comparable results, suggesting our results to be robust.

524

525 **5. Conclusion**

526 In conclusion, we found evidence that cumulative exposure to cold or hot temperatures
527 during pregnancy was associated with changes in head circumference size and growth
528 throughout gestation, with corresponding susceptibility periods during the first pregnancy
529 trimester. Considering the predicted exacerbation of climate change, the identified
530 transient effects on foetal development might become more prominent in magnitude and
531 duration. However, results need to be interpreted with caution since we found no
532 associations at birth, suggesting potential recovery of the identified changes. Future
533 research should explore the association between temperature exposure and foetal size and
534 growth further and replicate this study across different climatic regions and including
535 varying temperature profiles. Also, understanding when during pregnancy temperature
536 may exert its influence is crucial to further clarify physiological mechanisms and provides
537 a basis for developing strategies to mitigate the adverse health impacts experienced by
538 pregnant women and their children amid the escalating climate crisis.

539 **Funding**

540 Born in Bradford receives funding from by a joint grant from the UK Medical Research
541 Council (MRC) and UK Economic and Social Science Research Council (ESRC)
542 [MR/N024391/1]; the British Heart Foundation [CS/16/4/32482]; a Wellcome
543 Infrastructure Grant [WT101597MA]; The National Institute for Health Research under
544 its Applied Research Collaboration for Yorkshire and Humber [NIHR200166]. The views
545 expressed are those of the author(s), and not necessarily those of the NHS, the NIHR or
546 the Department of Health and Social Care. The authors acknowledge that Born in
547 Bradford is only possible because of the enthusiasm and commitment of the children and
548 parents in Born in Bradford. We are grateful to all participants, health professionals and
549 researchers who have made Born in Bradford happen.

550 The Generation R Study is conducted by the Erasmus Medical Center in close
551 collaboration with the Faculty of Social Sciences of the Erasmus University Rotterdam,
552 the Municipal Health Service Rotterdam area, Rotterdam, the Rotterdam Homecare
553 Foundation, Rotterdam, and the Stichting Trombosedienst & Artsenlaboratorium
554 Rijnmond (STAR- MDC), Rotterdam. We gratefully acknowledge the contribution of
555 children and parents, general practitioners, hospitals, midwives, and pharmacies in
556 Rotterdam. The general design of the Generation R Study is made possible by financial
557 support from the Erasmus Medical Center, Rotterdam; the Erasmus University Rotterdam;
558 the Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw); the
559 Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO); and the Ministry of Health,
560 Welfare and Sport. SS is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research
561 and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral
562 Fellowship Grant Agreement No. 101109136 (URBANE). Dr. El Marroun was supported
563 by Stichting Volksbond Rotterdam, the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research

564 (NWO) Aspasia grant (No: 015.016.056), and the European Union's Horizon 2020
565 Research and Innovation Program (HappyMums, Grant Agreement No: 101057390).

566 The INMA Project is funded by grants from Instituto de Salud Carlos III (Red
567 INMA G03/176, CB06/02/0041, FIS-FEDER: PI03/1615, PI04/1509, PI04/2018,
568 PI04/1112, PI04/1931, PI05/1079, PI05/1052, PI06/0867, PI06/1213, PI07/0314,
569 PI09/02647, PI09/00090, PI09/02311, PI11/01007, PI11/02591, PI11/02038, PI13/1944,
570 PI13/2032, PI13/02187, PI13/02429, PI14/00891, PI14/01687, PI16/1288, PI17/00663,
571 PI18/00909, PI18/01142, PI20/01695); from the UE (FP7-ENV-2011 cod 282957 and
572 HEALTH.2010.2.4.5-1); European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
573 programme ATHLETE project (grant agreement 874583); from Miguel Servet-FEDER
574 (CP11/00178, CP15/00025, and CPII16/00051, CPII18/00018); from Generalitat
575 Valenciana: FISABIO (UGP 15-230, UGP-15-244, and UGP-15-249); from the Alicia
576 Koplowitz Foundation 2017; from CIBERESP; from Fundación Cajastur and
577 Universidad de Oviedo; from the Department of Health of the Basque Government
578 (2005111093, 2009111069, 2013111089 and 2015111065); from the Provincial
579 Government of Gipuzkoa (DFG06/002, DFG08/001 and DFG15/221); annual agreements
580 with the municipalities of the Gipuzkoa study area (Zumarraga, Urretxu, Legazpi,
581 Azkoitia y Azpeitia y Beasain); and from Generalitat de Catalunya-CIRIT 1999SGR
582 00241. We received funding from the Agence Nationale de Securite Sanitaire de
583 l'Alimentation de l'Environnement et du Travail (EST-18 RF-25), acknowledge support
584 from the grant CEX2018-000806-S funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and
585 support from the Generalitat de Catalunya through the CERCA Program. Laura Granés
586 was funded by a Rio Hortega fellowship (CM22/00011) awarded by the Spanish Institute
587 of Health Carlos III. Delaney's research contribution reported in this publication was
588 supported by the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences under Award

589 Number R01ES034373 and by the National Institute on Aging under Award Number
590 R01AG066793. The content is solely the responsibility of the authors and does not
591 necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.

References

- Bakhtsiyarava, M., Ortigoza, A., Sánchez, B. N., Braverman-Bronstein, A., Kephart, J. L., Rodríguez López, S., Rodríguez, J., & Diez Roux, A. V. (2022). Ambient temperature and term birthweight in Latin American cities. *Environment International*, *167*, 107412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2022.107412>
- Barbour, L. A., & Hernandez, T. L. (2018). Maternal Lipids and Fetal Overgrowth: Making Fat from Fat. *Clinical Therapeutics*, *40*(10), 1638–1647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinthera.2018.08.007>
- Basagaña, X., Michael, Y., Lensky, I., Rubin, L., Grotto, I., Vadislavsky, E., Levi, Y., Amitai, E., & Agay-Shay, K. (2021). Low and High Ambient Temperatures during Pregnancy and Birth Weight among 624,940 Singleton Term Births in Israel (2010-2014): An Investigation of Potential Windows of Susceptibility. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *129*(10). <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP8117>
- Buckley, J. P., Samet, J. M., & Richardson, D. B. (2014). Does air pollution confound studies of temperature? In *Epidemiology* (Vol. 25, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000000051>
- Chen, X., Chen, S., Zhu, Z., Luo, J., Wang, H., Wulayin, M., Huang, C., Zhao, W., & Wang, Q. (2023). Identifying the critical windows and joint effects of temperature and PM2.5 exposure on small for gestational age. *Environment International*, *173*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.107832>
- Cornes, R. C., van der Schrier, G., van den Besselaar, E. J. M., & Jones, P. D. (2018). An Ensemble Version of the E-OBS Temperature and Precipitation Data Sets. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, *123*(17). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017JD028200>
- Cowell, W., Ard, N., Herrera, T., Medley, E. A., & Trasande, L. (2023). Ambient temperature, heat stress and fetal growth: A review of placenta-mediated mechanisms. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, *576*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2023.112000>
- Damhuis, S. E., Ganzevoort, W., & Gordijn, S. J. (2021). Abnormal Fetal Growth. *Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinics of North America*, *48*(2), 267–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ogc.2021.02.002>
- de Bont, J., Stafoggia, M., Nakstad, B., Hajat, S., Kovats, S., Part, C., Chersich, M., Luchters, S., Filippi, V., Stephansson, O., Ljungman, P., & Roos, N. (2022). Associations between ambient temperature and risk of preterm birth in Sweden: A comparison of analytical approaches. *Environmental Research*, *213*, 113586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.113586>
- de Graaf-Peters, V. B., & Hadders-Algra, M. (2006). Ontogeny of the human central nervous system: What is happening when? *Early Human Development*, *82*(4), 257–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2005.10.013>
- De Ridder, K., Lauwaet, D., & Maiheu, B. (2015). UrbClim - A fast urban boundary layer climate model. *Urban Climate*, *12*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2015.01.001>
- EEA. (2022, June 22). *Global and European temperatures*.
- European Environmental Agency. (2012). *Main climates of Europe*. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/climate>.
- Ferguson, K. K., Kamai, E. M., Cantonwine, D. E., Mukherjee, B., Meeker, J. D., & McElrath, T. F. (2018). Associations between repeated ultrasound measures of fetal growth and biomarkers of maternal oxidative stress and inflammation in pregnancy. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology*, *80*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/aji.13017>
- Freeman, J. V., Cole, T. J., Chinn, S., Jones, P. R. M., White, E. M., & Preece, M. A. (1995). Cross sectional stature and weight reference curves for the UK, 1990. *Archives of Disease in Childhood*, *73*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1136/adc.73.1.17>
- Gale, C. R., O'Callaghan, F. J., Bredow, M., & Martyn, C. N. (2006). The influence of head growth in fetal life, infancy, and childhood on intelligence at the ages of 4 and 8 years. *Pediatrics*, *118*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2005-2629>
- Gale, C. R., O'Callaghan, F. J., Godfrey, K. M., Law, C. M., & Martyn, C. N. (2004). Critical periods of brain growth and cognitive function in children. *Brain*, *127*(2). <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awh034>
- Galwey, N. W. (2009). A new measure of the effective number of tests, a practical tool for comparing families of non-independent significance tests. *Genetic Epidemiology*, *33*(7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/gepi.20408>
- García-Diéz, M., Lauwaet, D., Hooyberghs, H., Ballester, J., de Ridder, K., & Rodó, X. (2016). Advantages of using a fast urban boundary layer model as compared to a full mesoscale model to simulate the urban heat island of Barcelona. *Geoscientific Model Development*, *9*(12). <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-4439-2016>
- Gasparrini, A. (2014). Modeling exposure-lag-response associations with distributed lag non-linear models. *Statistics in Medicine*, *33*(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.5963>
- Gasparrini, A., Armstrong, B., & Kenward, M. G. (2010). Distributed lag non-linear models. *Statistics in Medicine*, *29*(21). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.3940>
- Georgis-Allemand, L., Pedersen, M., Bernard, C., Aguilera, I., Beelen, R. M. J., Chatzi, L., Cirach, M., Danileviciute, A., Dedele, A., Van Eijsden, M., Estarlich, M., Fernández-Somoano, A., Fernández, M. F., Forastiere, F.,

- Gehring, U., Grazuleviciene, R., Gruzieva, O., Heude, B., Hoek, G., ... Slama, R. (2017). The influence of meteorological factors and atmospheric pollutants on the risk of preterm birth. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 185(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kww141>
- Gurrin, L. C., Blake, K. V., Evans, S. F., & Newnham, J. P. (2001). Statistical measures of foetal growth using linear mixed models applied to the foetal origins hypothesis. *Statistics in Medicine*, 20(22). <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.891>
- Guxens, M., Ballester, F., Espada, M., Fernández, M. F., Grimalt, J. O., Ibarluzea, J., Olea, N., Rebagliato, M., Tardón, A., Torrent, M., Vioque, J., Vrijheid, M., & Sunyer, J. (2012). Cohort profile: The INMA-Infancia y Medio Ambiente-(environment and childhood) project. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 41(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyr054>
- Ha, S., Liu, D., Zhu, Y., Sherman, S., & Mendola, P. (2018). Acute Associations between Outdoor Temperature and Premature Rupture of Membranes. *Epidemiology*, 29(2). <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000000779>
- Hadlock, F. P., Harrist, R. B., Sharman, R. S., Deter, R. L., & Park, S. K. (1985). Estimation of fetal weight with the use of head, body, and femur measurements-A prospective study. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 151(3). [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378\(85\)90298-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378(85)90298-4)
- Hammami, A., Mazer Zumaeta, A., Syngelaki, A., Akolekar, R., & Nicolaides, K. H. (2018). Ultrasonographic estimation of fetal weight: development of new model and assessment of performance of previous models. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 52(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/uog.19066>
- Herrick, E., & Bordoni, B. (2023, May 1). *Embryology, Placenta*. StatPearls Publishing.
- Honaker, J., King, G., & Blackwell, M. (2012). *AMELIA II: A Program for Missing Data, Version 1.6.2*.
- Hough, I., Rolland, M., Guilbert, A., Seyve, E., Heude, B., Slama, R., Lyon-Caen, S., Pin, I., Chevrier, C., Kloog, I., & Lepeule, J. (2022). Early delivery following chronic and acute ambient temperature exposure: a comprehensive survival approach. *International Journal of Epidemiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyac190>
- Iñiguez, C., Esplugues, A., Sunyer, J., Basterrechea, M., Fernández-Somoano, A., Costa, O., Estarlich, M., Aguilera, I., Lertxundi, A., Tardón, A., Guxens, M., Murcia, M., Lopez-Espinosa, M. J., & Ballester, F. (2016). Prenatal exposure to NO₂ and ultrasound measures of fetal growth in the Spanish INMA cohort. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 124(2). <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1409423>
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*.
- Jakpor, O., Chevrier, C., Kloog, I., Benmerad, M., Giorgis-Allemand, L., Cordier, S., Seyve, E., Vicedo-Cabrera, A. M., Slama, R., Heude, B., Schwartz, J., & Lepeule, J. (2020). Term birthweight and critical windows of prenatal exposure to average meteorological conditions and meteorological variability. *Environment International*, 142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105847>
- Kimura, Y., Okamura, K., Watanabe, T., Takahashi, T., Haga, I., & Yajima, A. (1998). The effect of cold stress on uterine artery blood flow velocity waveforms in late pregnant women with and without preeclampsia. *Tohoku Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 186(2). <https://doi.org/10.1620/tjem.186.71>
- Kirwan, D. (2010). *NHS Fetal Anomaly Screening Programme: 18+0 to 20+6 Weeks Fetal Anomaly Scan National Standards and Guidance for England*.
- Kiserud, T., Piaggio, G., Carroli, G., Widmer, M., Carvalho, J., Neerup Jensen, L., Giordano, D., Cecatti, J. G., Abdel Aleem, H., Talegawkar, S. A., Benachi, A., Diemert, A., Tshetu Kitoto, A., Thinkhamrop, J., Lumbiganon, P., Tabor, A., Kriplani, A., Gonzalez Perez, R., Hecher, K., ... Platt, L. D. (2017). The World Health Organization Fetal Growth Charts: A Multinational Longitudinal Study of Ultrasound Biometric Measurements and Estimated Fetal Weight. *PLoS Medicine*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002220>
- Kooijman, M. N., Kruihof, C. J., van Duijn, C. M., Duijts, L., Franco, O. H., van IJzendoorn, M. H., de Jongste, J. C., Klaver, C. C. W., van der Lugt, A., Mackenbach, J. P., Moll, H. A., Peeters, R. P., Raat, H., Rings, E. H. H. M., Rivadeneira, F., van der Schroeff, M. P., Steegers, E. A. P., Tiemeier, H., Uitterlinden, A. G., ... Jaddoe, V. W. V. (2016). The Generation R Study: design and cohort update 2017. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 31(12). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-016-0224-9>
- Kovacs, C. S. (2011). Bone development in the fetus and neonate: Role of the calciotropic hormones. *Current Osteoporosis Reports*, 9(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11914-011-0073-0>
- Lauwaet, D., de Ridder, K., Saeed, S., Brisson, E., Chatterjee, F., van Lipzig, N. P. M., Maiheu, B., & Hooyberghs, H. (2016). Assessing the current and future urban heat island of Brussels. *Urban Climate*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2015.11.008>
- Lauwaet, D., Hooyberghs, H., Maiheu, B., Lefebvre, W., Driesen, G., van Looy, S., & de Ridder, K. (2015). Detailed urban heat island projections for cities worldwide: Dynamical downscaling CMIP5 global climate models. *Climate*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli3020391>
- Leibovitz, Z., Lerman-Sagie, T., & Haddad, L. (2022). Fetal Brain Development: Regulating Processes and Related Malformations. In *Life* (Vol. 12, Issue 6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/life12060809>

- Leung, M., Laden, F., Coull, B. A., Modest, A. M., Hacker, M. R., Wylie, B. J., Iyer, H. S., Hart, J. E., Wei, Y., Schwartz, J., Weisskopf, M. G., & Papatheodorou, S. (2022). Ambient temperature during pregnancy and fetal growth in Eastern Massachusetts, USA. *International Journal of Epidemiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyac228>
- Liao, L., Wei, X., Liu, M., Gao, Y., Yin, Y., & Zhou, R. (2023). The Association Between Season and Hypertensive Disorders in Pregnancy: a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. In *Reproductive Sciences* (Vol. 30, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43032-022-01010-0>
- McElroy, S., Ilango, S., Dimitrova, A., Gershunov, A., & Benmarhnia, T. (2022). Extreme heat, preterm birth, and stillbirth: A global analysis across 14 lower-middle income countries. *Environment International*, 158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106902>
- Moriyama, M., Hugentobler, W. J., & Iwasaki, A. (2020). Seasonality of Respiratory Viral Infections. *Annual Review of Virology*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-virology-012420-022445>
- Mork, D., & Wilson, A. (2022). Treed distributed lag nonlinear models. *Biostatistics*, 23(3). <https://doi.org/10.1093/biostatistics/kxaa051>
- Niklasson, A., Ericson, A., Fryer, J. G., Karlberg, J., Lawrence, C., & Karlberg, P. (1991). An update of the Swedish reference standards for weight, length and head circumference at birth for given gestational age (1977-1981). *Acta Paediatrica Scandinavica*, 80(8-9). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.1991.tb11945.x>
- Pardi, G., & Cetin, I. (2006). Human fetal growth and organ development: 50 years of discoveries. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 194(4), 1088-1099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2005.12.056>
- Pinheiro, J. C., & Bates, D. M. (2000). Mixed-Effects Models in S and S-Plus: Statistics and Computing. In *Mixed-Effects Models in S and S-PLUS*.
- Pitakkarnkul, S., Phaloprakarn, C., Wiriyasirivaj, B., Manusirivithaya, S., & Tangjitgamol, S. (2011). Seasonal variation in the prevalence of preeclampsia. In *Journal of the Medical Association of Thailand* (Vol. 94, Issue 11). https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_132_17
- Reid, C. E., Snowden, J. M., Kontgis, C., & Tager, I. B. (2012). The role of ambient ozone in epidemiologic studies of heat-related mortality. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 120(12). <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1205251>
- Rhew, I. C., Vander Stoep, A., Kearney, A., Smith, N. L., & Dunbar, M. D. (2011). Validation of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index as a Measure of Neighborhood Greenness. *Annals of Epidemiology*, 21(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annepidem.2011.09.001>
- Rocque, R. J., Beaudoin, C., Ndjaboue, R., Cameron, L., Poirier-Bergeron, L., Poulin-Rheault, R. A., Fallon, C., Tricco, A. C., & Wittman, H. O. (2021). Health effects of climate change: An overview of systematic reviews. *BMJ Open*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-046333>
- Samuels, L., Nakstad, B., Roos, N., Bonell, A., Chersich, M., Havenith, G., Luchters, S., Day, L. T., Hirst, J. E., Singh, T., Elliott-Sale, K., Hetem, R., Part, C., Sawry, S., Le Roux, J., & Kovats, S. (2022). Physiological mechanisms of the impact of heat during pregnancy and the clinical implications: review of the evidence from an expert group meeting. In *International Journal of Biometeorology* (Vol. 66, Issue 8). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-022-02301-6>
- Soultanakis-Aligianni, H. N. (2003). Thermoregulation during exercise in pregnancy. In *Clinical Obstetrics and Gynecology* (Vol. 46, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1097/00003081-200306000-00023>
- Steegers-Theunissen, R. P. M., Twigt, J., Pestinger, V., & Sinclair, K. D. (2013). The periconceptual period, reproduction and long-term health of offspring: the importance of one-carbon metabolism. *Human Reproduction Update*, 19(6), 640-655. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humupd/dmt041>
- Sun, Y., Zhang, M., Chen, S., Zhang, W., Zhang, Y., Su, S., Zhang, E., Sun, L., Yang, K., Wang, J., Yue, W., Wu, Q., Liu, R., & Yin, C. (2023). Potential impact of ambient temperature on maternal blood pressure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy: A nationwide multicenter study based on the China birth cohort. *Environmental Research*, 227, 115733. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.115733>
- Syed, S., O'Sullivan, T. L., & Phillips, K. P. (2022). Extreme Heat and Pregnancy Outcomes: A Scoping Review of the Epidemiological Evidence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19042412>
- Thompson, R. A., & Nelson, C. A. (2001). Developmental science and the media: Early brain development. *American Psychologist*, 56(1). <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.56.1.5>
- Usselman, C. W., Wakefield, P. K., Skow, R. J., Stickland, M. K., Chari, R. S., Julian, C. G., Steinback, C. D., & Davenport, M. H. (2015). Regulation of sympathetic nerve activity during the cold pressor test in normotensive pregnant and nonpregnant women. *Hypertension*, 66(4). <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.115.05964>
- Veenema, R. J., Hoepner, L. A., & Geer, L. A. (2023). Climate Change-Related Environmental Exposures and Perinatal and Maternal Health Outcomes in the U.S. In *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* (Vol. 20, Issue 3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20031662>

- Verbruggen, S. W., Kainz, B., Shelmerdine, S. C., Hajnal, J. V., Rutherford, M. A., Arthurs, O. J., Phillips, A. T. M., & Nowlan, N. C. (2018). Stresses and strains on the human fetal skeleton during development. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, *15*(138). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2017.0593>
- Verburg, B. O., Steegers, E. A. P., De Ridder, M., Snijders, R. J. M., Smith, E., Hofman, A., Moll, H. A., Jaddoe, V. W. V., & Witteman, J. C. M. (2008). New charts for ultrasound dating of pregnancy and assessment of fetal growth: Longitudinal data from a population-based cohort study. *Ultrasound in Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *31*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/uog.5225>
- Wang, & Zhao. (2010). Chapter 2, Placental Blood Circulation. In *Vascular Biology of the Placenta*. Morgan & Claypool Life Sciences.
- Weisskopf, M. G., Sparrow, D., Hu, H., & Power, M. C. (2015). Biased exposure-health effect estimates from selection in cohort studies: Are environmental studies at particular risk? *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *123*(11). <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1408888>
- WHO. (2021, October 30). *Climate change and health*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/climate-change-and-health>.
- Wright, J., Small, N., Raynor, P., Tuffnell, D., Bhopal, R., Cameron, N., Fairley, L., A Lawlor, D., Parslow, R., Petherick, E. S., Pickett, K. E., Waiblinger, D., & West, J. (2013). Cohort profile: The born in bradford multi-ethnic family cohort study. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, *42*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dys112>
- Yitshak-Sade, M., Kloog, I., Schwartz, J. D., Novack, V., Erez, O., & Just, A. C. (2021). The effect of prenatal temperature and PM2.5 exposure on birthweight: Weekly windows of exposure throughout the pregnancy. *Environment International*, *155*, 106588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106588>
- Yu, G., Yang, L., Liu, M., Wang, C., Shen, X., Fan, L., & Zhang, J. (2023). Extreme Temperature Exposure and Risks of Preterm Birth Subtypes Based on a Nationwide Survey in China. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *131*(8). <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP10831>

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Ambient Air Temperature Exposure and Foetal Size and Growth in Three European Birth Cohorts

Esmée Essers, Laura Granés, Scott Delaney, Joan Ballester, Susana Santos, Sami Petricola, Tiffany C Yang, Ana Fernández-Somoano, Ainhoa Bereziartua, Ferran Ballester, Adonina Tardón, Martine Vrijheid, Aitana Lertxundi, Rosie McEachan, Hanan El Marroun, Henning Tiemeier, Carmen Iñiguez, Mònica Guxens

Figure S1	Flowchart of the study participants in the three European birth cohorts	3
Methods S1	Detailed description of the temperature exposure assessment	4
Figure S2	Placement of the 30 x 30 km domains within the regions of the three European birth cohorts	6
Table S1	Descriptives of the gestational age throughout pregnancy in the three European birth cohort	7
Figure S3	Directed acyclic graph of the temperature and foetal size and growth association	8
Table S2	Details of the expectation-maximization imputation	9
Table S3	Characteristics of the participants in observed and expectation-maximization imputed datasets in the three European birth cohorts	10
Table S4	Population characteristics of subjects included and not included in the analysis in the three European birth cohorts	11
Table S5	List of variables explored in logistic regression model to calculate inverse probability of attrition weights in the study population and those included in the final estimations in the three European birth cohorts	12
Figure S4	Distribution of inverse probability weights for each study population in the three European birth cohorts	13
Table S6	Average ambient temperature associated with various percentile distributions during weeks 1 to 18, 28, and 32 of pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts and the averaged percentiles used for the meta-analysis	14
Table S7	Average foetal size and growth metrics and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts	15
Table S8	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and foetal size metrics in standard deviation scores in the three European birth cohorts	16
Table S9	Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure at the 2.5 th or 97.5 th percentile during each week of pregnancy and head circumference SDS at late pregnancy	18
Table S10	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and foetal growth metrics from mid to late pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts	19
Table S11	Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure at the 2.5 th percentile (4.2 °C) during each week of pregnancy and head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy in centimetres per week	20

Table S12	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and birth outcomes standard deviation scores in two or three European birth cohorts	21
Figure S5	Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and head circumference at birth and birth length in the two European birth cohorts	22
Figure S6	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts, with knots placed at the 10 th and 90 th percentile of temperature distribution in the exposure-response relationship	23
Figure S7	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts, with the lag-response relationship modelled linearly	24
Figure S8	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts, with the lag-response relationship with 2 knots	25
Figure S9	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts only including mothers with available temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 38 of pregnancy	26
Figure S10	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and birth weight, head circumference at birth, and birth length in the three European birth cohorts, using a lag period of 18- or 28-weeks during pregnancy	27
Figure S11	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts, stratified by foetal sex	28
Figure S12	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts, only for mothers who had a national origin of the respective cohort	30
Figure S13	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and head circumference at late pregnancy in each cohort/region of the three European birth cohorts	31
Figure S14	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy in each cohort/region of the three European birth cohorts	32
Figure S15	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy, and birth outcomes in two European birth cohorts (Born in Bradford excluded)	33
Figure S16	Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid and late pregnancy, and foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts, only for mothers who had available data at both the mid and late pregnancy assessments.	34
References		35

	Estimated Foetal Weight	Head Circumference	Femur Length
Mid pregnancy	18,092	21,197	21,272
Late pregnancy	15,261	15,263	15,785
At birth	22950*	7,499	6,722**
Growth from mid to late pregnancy	13,277	14,898	15,503

* birthweight, ** birth length

Figure S1. Flowchart of the study participants in the three European birth cohorts.

Methods S1. Detailed description of the temperature exposure assessment.

Accurate assessment of ambient air temperature was ensured via the UrbClim™ model (De Ridder et al., 2015). This model uses urban physics coupled with a 3D atmospheric boundary layer module that includes information on the urban structure (e.g., vegetation, land use and cover) to generate climate data at a high temporal (hourly) and spatial (100 x 100 metres) resolution (De Ridder et al., 2015; Golan et al., 2018). UrbClim™ has been successfully validated in various European countries, including Spain and the UK (García-Diéz et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al., 2015, 2016).

The model is developed for domains of 30 x 30 km. In this study, the location of a singular domain for each region (except for Generation R, where two domains were placed) was placed based on the geographical area where the maximum number of participants lived during pregnancy (96.6% for BiB, 99.2% for Generation R, and 95.7%, 99.3%, 99.3%, and 96.2% for INMA-Asturias, INMA-Gipuzkoa, INMA-Sabadell, and INMA-Valencia, respectively). Temperature was calculated for the years of pregnancy: July 2006 until June 2011 for BiB, August 2001 until January 2006 for Generation R, and August 2003 until August 2008 for INMA. The hourly temperature data was converted into daily data based on the Coordinated Universal Time and estimated at the geocoded address where the mother lived during her pregnancy period, accounting for changes in address.

The six model domains were set up using the European Terrestrial Reference System 1989 (EPSG 3035) as the coordinate system (Annoni et al., 2001). To obtain the most realistic representation for historical climate for the regions, land cover maps (identifying the spatial distribution of land cover types) were used. For BiB and Generation R, the 2006 European CORINE land cover map was used (Copernicus, n.d.) and for INMA, the 2005 Sistema de Información de Ocupación del Suelo en España (SOISE) land cover map was used (SOISE, n.d.). Annex A shows the conversion of the SOISE and CORINE classifications into the 15 classes of land cover in the UrbClim™ model. The model also uses Copernicus Land Imperviousness datasets (soil sealing maps), the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index from the TERRA satellite platforms MODIS instrument (vegetation cover maps), and data provided by the European Centre for Medium-range Weather

Forecasting ERA5 reanalysis (background meteorology) as input data (Copernicus, n.d.; ECMWF, n.d.; NASA, n.d.).

Annex A. Land use conversion tables from SOISE (using the CODIIGE codes) and CORINE classes into the fifteen UrbClim™ classes.

CODIIGE code	English name	UrbClim code	UrbClim class	CORINE code	English name	UrbClim code	UrbClim class
111	Helmet	1	Urban	1	Continuous urban fabric	1	Urban
112	Expansion	1	Urban	2	Discont. urban fabric	2	Suburban
113	Discontinuous	2	Suburban	3	Industrial or commercial units	3	Industrial
114	Urban green zone	4	Urban green	4	Road and rail networks and ass. land	3	Industrial
121	Agricultural and / or livestock facility	3	Industrial	5	Port areas	3	Industrial
122	Forestry facility	3	Industrial	6	Airports	3	Industrial
123	Mining extraction	3	Industrial	7	Mineral extraction sites	3	Industrial
130	Industrial	3	Industrial	8	Dump sites	3	Industrial
140	Endowment service	2	Suburban	9	Construction sites	3	Industrial
150	Agricultural settlement and orchard	2	Suburban	10	Green urban areas	4	Urban green
161	Road or rail network	3	Industrial	11	Sport and leisure facilities	4	Urban green
162	port	3	Industrial	12	Non-irrigated arable land	8	Cropland
163	Airport	3	Industrial	13	Permanent irrigated land	8	Cropland
171	Supply infrastructure	3	Industrial	14	Rice fields	8	Cropland
172	Waste infrastructure	3	Industrial	15	Vineyards	9	Shrubland
210	Herbaceous crop	8	Cropland	16	Fruit trees and berry plantations	10	Woodland
220	Greenhouse	3	Industrial	17	Olive groves	10	Woodland
231	Citrus fruit	11	Broadleaf trees	18	Pastures	7	Grassland
232	Non-citrus fruit	11	Broadleaf trees	19	Annual crops ass. w/ permanent crops	8	Cropland
233	Vineyard	9	Shrubland	20	Complex cultivation patterns	8	Cropland
234	Olive grove	11	Broadleaf trees	21	Heterogeneous agricultural areas	8	Cropland
235	Other woody crops	10	Woodland	22	Agro-forestry areas	10	Woodland
236	Woody crop mix	9	Shrubland	23	Broad-leaved forest	11	Broadleaf trees
240	Meadow	7	Grassland	24	Coniferous forest	12	Needleleaf trees
250	Crop combination	8	Cropland	25	Mixed forest	11	Broadleaf trees
260	Combination of crops with vegetation	8	Cropland	26	Natural grasslands	7	Grassland
311	Hardwood forest	10	Woodland	27	Moors and heathland	10	Woodland
313	Mixed forest	10	Woodland	28	Sclerophyllous vegetation	9	Shrubland
312	Coniferous forest	12	Needleleaf trees	29	Transit. woodland-shrub	9	Shrubland
320	Pasture or grassland	7	Grassland	30	Beaches, dunes, sand	6	Bare soil
330	Scrub	9	Shrubland	31	Bare rocks	6	Bare soil
340	Vegetation combination	9	Shrubland	32	Sparsely vegetated areas	9	Shrubland
351	Beach, dune or sand	6	Bare soil	33	Burnt areas	6	Bare soil
352	Roquedo	6	Bare soil	34	Glaciers & perpetual snow	5	Snow/ice
353	Temporarily deforested by fires	6	Bare soil	35	Inland marshes	9	Shrubland
354	Bare ground	6	Bare soil	36	Peat bogs	9	Shrubland
411	Wet and swampy area	7	Grassland	37	Salt marshes	7	Grassland
412	Peatbog	7	Grassland	38	Salines	7	Grassland
413	Marsh	7	Grassland	39	Intertidal flats	6	Bare soil
414	Saline	7	Grassland	40	Water courses	13	River
514	Artificial water foil	14	Inland water body	41	Water bodies	14	Inland water bo
511	Water course	13	River	42	Coastal lagoons	15	Sea
512	Lake or lagoon	14	Inland water body	43	Estuaries	15	Sea
513	Reservoir	14	Inland water body	44	Sea and ocean	15	Sea
515	Sea	15	Sea				
516	Glacier and / or perpetual snow	5	Snow/Ice				

Figure S2. Placement of the 30x30 km domains within the regions of the three European birth cohorts.

Table S1. Descriptives of the gestational ages throughout pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts.

	Gestational age at mid pregnancy				Gestational age at late pregnancy				Gestational age at birth			
	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>N</i>
Born in Bradford	20.4 (1.2)	14.0	27.9	12186	32.8 (2.8)	28.0	42.7	6148	39.6 (1.7)	29.0	44.7	12701
Generation R	20.6 (1.4)	14.0	27.9	8016	30.5 (1.1)	28.0	39.3	7900	39.9 (1.6)	31.1	43.7	8317
INMA-Asturias	20.5 (1.1)	14.7	23.0	468	33.5 (1.1)	28.1	36.0	467	39.5 (1.4)	35.0	42.9	469
INMA-Gipuzkoa	21.0 (1.1)	14.0	26.9	583	33.9 (1.2)	28.1	38.4	571	39.8 (1.4)	33.0	42.6	599
INMA-Sabadell	20.7 (1.7)	14.0	27.1	607	34.0 (1.1)	28.1	40.0	603	39.7 (1.4)	32.4	42.3	611
INMA-Valencia	20.2 (1.0)	14.0	27.6	705	32.2 (1.0)	28.1	38.7	683	39.7 (1.5)	32.1	42.4	709

Abbreviations: Max, maximum; Min, minimum; SD, standard deviation.

Figure S3. Directed acyclic graph of the temperature and foetal size and growth association.

The green node with a triangle represents the exposure and the blue node with an I represents the outcome. Red nodes and arrows represent potential confounding variables and pathways, blue nodes represent ancestors of the outcome, and yellow nodes ancestors of the exposure. Air pollution can be seen as a potential mediator with its biasing pathway in green.

Table S2. Details of the expectation-maximization imputation.

EXPECTATION-MAXIMIZATION IMPUTATION
Software used and key setting: R (version 4.0.0; R Core Team (2020)) – Amelia package
Number of imputed datasets created: 1
Sample size for imputation: 12,701 for BiB; 8,319 for Generation R and 469, 599, 611, and 709 for INMA-Asturias, INMA-Gipuzkoa, INMA-Sabadell, and INMA-Valencia, respectively
Variables with repeated measures averaged into one value for imputation: ambient air temperature, apparent temperature, urban heat island index, relative humidity, estimated foetal weight (EFW) / birth weight, head circumference (HC), femur length (FL) / birth length
Variables used as predictors for the imputation: foetal sex, month of conception, maternal age, paternal age*, maternal and paternal educational level, maternal and paternal* national origin, maternal smoking during pregnancy, maternal parity, maternal alcohol use during pregnancy, maternal folic acid use periconceptionally*, family status, maternal and paternal* height, maternal pre-pregnancy weight, paternal weight*, household surrounding greenness, monthly household income**, all averaged variables mentioned above and the EFW, HC, and FL growth from mid to late pregnancy. <i>* Not used in the Born in Bradford imputation due to unavailability (folic acid use) or > 40% missing</i> <i>** Only used in the imputation for the Generation R cohort due to availability</i>
Diagnostics: Visual inspection by checking convergence with convergence plots.
References: (Honaker et al., 2012)

Table S3. Characteristics of the participants in observed and expectation-maximization imputed datasets in the three European birth cohorts.

	Born in Bradford (N = 12,701)			Generation R (N = 8,319)			INMA											
							Asturias (N = 469)			Gipuzkoa (N = 599)			Sabadell (N = 611)			Valencia (N = 709)		
	obs.	imp.	% imp.	obs.	imp.	% imp.	obs.	imp.	% imp.	obs.	imp.	% imp.	obs.	imp.	% imp.	obs.	imp.	% imp.
<i>Maternal Characteristics</i>																		
Age (years)	27.4 (5.6)	27.5 (5.6)	17.3	29.7 (5.3)	-	0.0	31.5 (4.4)	-	0.0	31.4 (3.6)	-	0.0	30.2 (4.4)	30.2 (4.4)	0.2	29.8 (4.5)	-	0.0
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	26.0 (5.7)	26.0 (5.7)	21.4	23.6 (4.3)	23.7 (4.4)	19.2	23.8 (4.3)	-	0.0	22.9 (3.6)	-	0.0	23.7 (4.5)	-	0.0	23.8 (4.7)	-	0.0
Education level			23.9			8.6			0.0			0.3			0.5			0.0
High	27.6	28.8		42.3	41.1		36.5	-		51.1	51.3		29.0	29.1		23.4	-	
Medium	15.6	17.1		30.8	30.4		44.8	-		35.7	35.6		43.0	42.9		42.2	-	
Low	56.8	54.1		26.9	28.6		18.8	-		13.2	13.2		28.0	28.0		34.4	-	
National/ethnic origin			4.0			5.0			0.0			0.0			0.7			0.0
Country of cohort	41.7	41.0		49.6	48.1		96.4	-		95.8	-		89.0	88.9		88.2	-	
South Asian	54.0	53.5		na	na		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Black	2.1	2.3		na	na		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Mixed	2.1	2.3		na	na		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Morocco	na	na		6.9	7.3		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Suriname / Dutch Antilles	na	na		12.3	12.7		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Turkey	na	na		9.4	9.9		na	-		na	-		na	na		na	-	
Europe	na	na		na	na		1.1	-		1.5	-		2.5	2.6		3.1	-	
Latin America	na	na		na	na		1.9	-		2.5	-		8.2	8.2		8.2	-	
Other	0.8	0.9		21.7	22.0		0.6	-		0.2	-		0.3	0.3		0.6	-	
Alcohol use during pregnancy			17.6			10.4			0.0			0.7			0.2			0.0
Never	80.2	77.3		47.6	48.1		89.1	-		82.2	82.3		77.9	77.9		74.5	-	
Until pregnancy known	6.7	7.7		12.9	13.4		5.3	-		6.0	6.0		5.7	5.7		7.8	-	
Occasionally	9.5	10.6		32.0	31.4		5.5	-		11.8	11.7		16.4	16.4		17.8	-	
Frequent	3.6	4.4		7.4	7.2		na	-		na	-		na	0.0		na	-	
Smoking during pregnancy			17.5			12.3			5.3			2.7			1.8			0.3
Never	83.71	81.7		72.9	71.1		71.4	70.6		76.3	75.6		69.7	69.4		59.0	59.0	
Until pregnancy known	2.9	3.6		8.6	9.4		11.0	11.3		12.2	12.5		16.0	16.4		18.2	18.3	
Continued	13.4	14.7		18.5	19.5		17.6	18.1		11.5	11.9		14.3	14.2		22.8	22.7	
Parity			3.6			1.1			0.0			0.0			0.3			0.0
0 children	39.3	39.4		55.5	55.3		61.0	-		53.8	-		56.5	56.3		55.0	-	
1 child	29.0	29.1		30.0	30.1		33.9	-		40.1	-		37.1	37.3		36.4	-	
2+ children	31.7	31.5		14.5	14.6		5.1	-		6.2	-		6.4	6.4		8.6	-	
Family status (couple vs. single parent)	83.9	82.7	17.5	85.6	84.6	8.8	98.1	-	0.0	99.3	-	0.0	98.8	98.9	0.2	97.6	-	0.0
<i>Paternal Characteristics</i>																		
Education level			38.4			39.6			0.9			1.0			1.0			0.4
High	33.4	30.7		50.9	41.6		22.8	22.6		26.3	26.0		21.2	21.3		14.9	15.1	
Medium	13.7	15.6		26.4	29.2		46.2	46.3		49.1	49.1		43.5	43.4		38.2	38.2	
Low	53.0	53.7		22.6	29.2		31.0	31.1		24.6	24.9		35.4	35.4		46.9	46.7	
<i>Household Characteristics</i>																		
Surrounding greenness	0.2 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.2	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	10.5	0.4 (0.1)	-	0.0	0.4 (0.1)	-	0.0	0.2 (0.1)	-	0.0	0.2 (0.1)	-	0.0

Values are percentage for categorical and mean (standard deviation) for continuous variables. Abbreviations: imp, imputed; na, not available; obs, observed.

Table S4. Population characteristics of subjects included and not included in the analysis in the three European birth cohorts.

	Born in Bradford			Generation R			INMA											
	Included (N = 12,701)	Not included (N = 498)	P-value	Included (N = 8,319)	Not included (N = 418)	P-value	Asturias			Gipuzkoa			Sabadell			Valencia		
							Included (N = 469)	Not included (N = 25)	P-value	Included (N = 599)	Not included (N = 39)	P-value	Included (N = 611)	Not included (N = 46)	P-value	Included (N = 709)	Not included (N = 118)	P-value
Child Characteristics																		
Sex (female vs. male)	48.5	47.2	0.607	49.6	48.9	0.851	48.0	37.5	0.568	49.6	58.3	0.758	49.6	44.4	1.00	47.2	44.9	0.780
Season of conception			0.652			0.962			0.111			0.262			0.739			0.025
Summer	26.2	21.1		23.7	22.0		21.3	43.8		30.2	45.5		28.6	44.4		22.7	7.8	
Fall	25.9	26.5		27.4	29.7		28.6	25.0		23.0	36.4		23.4	22.2		20.7	26.0	
Winter	25.2	28.1		26.7	26.4		26.2	6.2		16.7	0.0		21.0	11.1		31.6	36.4	
Spring	26.2	24.3		22.2	22.0		23.9	25.0		30.0	18.2		27.0	22.2		25.0	29.9	
Maternal Characteristics																		
Age (years)	27.4 (5.6)	26.0 (5.6)	< 0.001	29.7 (5.3)	28.0 (5.7)	< 0.001	31.5 (4.4)	32.0 (3.8)	0.616	31.4 (3.6)	30.6 (4.9)	0.353	30.2 (4.4)	30.4 (6.0)	0.854	29.8 (4.5)	29.8 (5.3)	0.965
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	26.0 (5.7)	25.7 (5.8)	0.195	23.6 (4.3)	24.2 (4.9)	0.137	23.8 (4.3)	24.1 (4.2)	0.797	22.9 (3.6)	24.2 (4.3)	0.048	23.7 (4.5)	24.2 (4.4)	0.982	23.8 (4.7)	23.3 (4.3)	0.357
Education level			0.675			0.001			0.050			0.099			0.111			0.512
High	27.6	25.9		42.3	32.0		36.5	62.5		51.1	33.3		29.0	20.0		23.4	18.6	
Medium	15.6	15.1		30.8	35.8		44.8	37.5		35.7	48.7		43.0	37.8		42.2	44.1	
Low	56.8	59.0		26.9	32.3		18.8	0.0		13.2	18.0		28.0	42.2		34.4	37.3	
National/ethnic origin			0.923			< 0.001			0.027			0.407			0.345			0.018
Country of cohort																		
Asia	41.1	39.6		49.6	31.8		96.4	91.7		95.8	92.3		89.0	82.2		88.2	87.3	
Morocco	54.0	55.0		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na	
Morocco	na	na		6.9	7.7		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na	
Suriname / Dutch Antilles	na	na		12.3	20.3		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na	
Turkey	na	na		9.4	7.2		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na	
Other	5.0	5.4		21.7	33.0		3.6	8.3		4.2	7.7		11.0	17.8		11.8	12.7	
Alcohol use during pregnancy			0.541			< 0.001			0.578			0.745			0.080			0.272
Never	80.2	79.5		47.6	56.4		89.1	100.0		82.2	75.0		77.9	0.0		74.5	68.8	
Until pregnancy known	6.7	8.1		12.9	18.5		5.3	0.0		6.0	12.5		5.7	100.0		7.8	18.2	
Occasionally	9.5	9.8		32.0	23.3		5.5	0.0		11.8	12.5		16.4	0.0		17.8	13.0	
Frequent	3.6	2.7		7.4	1.8		na	na		na	na		na	na		na	na	
Smoking during pregnancy			0.168			0.386			0.642			0.663			0.993			0.744
Never	83.7	80.4		72.9	69.5		71.4	83.3		76.3	68.8		69.7	69.2		59.0	60.0	
Until pregnancy known	2.9	2.9		8.6	10.0		11.0	8.3		12.2	12.5		16.0	15.4		18.2	15.0	
Continued	13.4	16.6		18.5	20.5		17.6	8.3		11.5	18.8		14.3	15.4		22.8	25.0	
Paternal Characteristics																		
Parity			0.005			0.110			0.643			0.380			0.157			0.860
0 children	39.3	45.9		55.5	59.5		61.0	62.5		53.8	59.0		56.5	47.7		55.0	57.6	
1 child	29.0	28.6		30.0	25.1		33.9	37.5		40.1	30.8		37.1	38.6		36.4	33.9	
2+ children	31.7	25.5		14.5	15.4		5.1	0.0		6.2	10.3		6.4	13.6		8.6	8.5	
Family status (couple vs. single parent)	83.9	79.4	0.019	85.6	75.2	< 0.001	98.1	93.8	0.761	99.3	100.0	1.000	98.8	95.6	0.242	97.6	97.5	1.000
Paternal Characteristics																		
Education level			0.633			0.022			0.279			0.057			0.133			0.858
High	33.4	32.9		50.9	39.2		22.8	31.3		26.3	25.6		21.2	25.6		14.9	12.9	
Medium	13.7	15.6		26.4	35.4		46.2	56.3		49.1	33.3		43.5	27.9		38.2	38.8	
Low	53.0	51.5		22.6	25.4		31.0	12.5		24.6	41.0		35.4	46.5		46.9	48.3	
Household Characteristics																		
Surrounding greenness	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.005	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.203	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.2)	0.262	0.4 (0.1)	0.4 (0.1)	0.126	0.2 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)	0.236	0.2 (0.1)	0.2 (0.1)	0.337

Values are percentage for categorical and mean (standard deviation) for continuous variables. P-value was obtained using the χ^2 test for categorical variables, two-sample t-test for normally distributed, and Wilcoxon Rank Sum test for non-normally distributed (body mass index) continuous variables, bolded values indicate significance at the 0.05 level. Na, not available.

Table S5. List of variables explored in logistic regression model to calculate inverse probability of attrition weights in the study population, and those included (X) in the final estimations in the three European birth cohorts.

Variables Explored	Born in Bradford	Generation R	INMA			
			Asturias	Gipuzkoa	Sabadell	Valencia
Child gender						
Child month of conception		X				
Maternal age	X	X		X		X
Paternal age*					X	X
Maternal national origin		X			X	
Paternal national origin*						X
Maternal education level			X	X		
Paternal education level				X	X	
Maternal body mass index		X		X		X
Paternal body mass index*				X		X
Smoking use during pregnancy						
Alcohol use during pregnancy	X	X		X		X
Folic acid use periconceptionally*					X	
Maternal parity					X	
Family status		X	X		X	
Household monthly income**						
Residential surrounding greenness	X		X	X	X	

* Not explored in the Born in Bradford cohort due to unavailability (folic acid) or > 40% missing (other variables)

** Only explored in the Generation R cohort due to availability

Figure S4. Distribution of inverse probability weights for each study population in the three European birth cohorts.

Table S6. Average ambient temperature (°C) associated with various percentile distributions during weeks 1 to 18, 28, and 32 of pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts and the averaged percentiles used for the meta-analysis.

	Percentile	Born in Bradford (<i>n</i> = 12,701)	Generation R (<i>n</i> = 8,319)	INMA				Meta-Analysis Sample (<i>n</i> = 23,408)
				Asturias (<i>n</i> = 469)	Gipuzkoa (<i>n</i> = 599)	Sabadell (<i>n</i> = 611)	Valencia (<i>n</i> = 709)	
Weeks 1 to 18	2.5	0.5	1.1	6.8	4.7	5.3	6.7	4.2
	25	5.7	7.1	11.5	10.0	10.1	11.9	9.4
	50	9.5	11.8	15.6	14.4	17.2	17.6	14.3
	75	13.7	17.0	19.2	18.4	22.4	24.3	19.2
	97.5	16.8	23.1	22.5	23.9	27.8	28.9	23.8
Weeks 1 to 28	2.5	0.5	1.1	6.7	4.7	5.3	6.7	4.2
	25	5.7	7.1	11.3	10.0	10.1	11.8	9.3
	50	9.4	11.6	15.4	14.8	17.3	17.1	14.3
	75	13.7	16.9	19.1	18.5	22.4	24.2	19.1
	97.5	16.8	23.1	22.4	24.3	27.8	28.9	23.9
Weeks 1 to 32	2.5	0.5	1.1	6.6	4.8	5.3	7.0	4.2
	25	5.7	6.9	10.8	10.5	10.3	11.7	9.3
	50	9.2	11.3	14.9	15.6	17.4	15.7	14.0
	75	13.6	16.6	18.8	18.9	22.5	23.5	19.0
	97.5	16.8	23.0	22.4	24.9	27.5	28.8	23.9

Table S7. Average foetal size and growth metrics and birth outcomes in the three European birth cohorts.

	<i>Unit</i>	Born in Bradford		Generation R		INMA - Asturias	
		<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>
Foetal size							
EFW at mid pregnancy	grams	360 (102)	8011	379 (104)	7737	380 (62)	466
EFW at late pregnancy	grams	1985 (543)	5202	1610 (249)	7771	2242 (297)	466
HC at mid pregnancy	cm	17.9 (1.5)	12069	17.9 (1.7)	7937	18.0 (1.3)	465
HC at late pregnancy	cm	30.2 (2.1)	5557	28.5 (1.2)	7811	30.5 (1.4)	466
FL at mid pregnancy	cm	3.3 (0.3)	12033	3.3 (0.4)	7960	3.4 (0.3)	468
FL at late pregnancy	cm	6.2 (0.6)	5934	5.8 (0.3)	7879	6.5 (0.3)	466
Foetal growth							
EFW growth from mid to late pregnancy	grams/week	131.9 (23.0)	3719	125.9 (18.3)	7297	142.9 (18.6)	463
HC growth from mid to late pregnancy	cm/week	1.0 (0.1)	5316	1.1 (0.1)	7485	1.0 (0.1)	462
FL growth from mid to late pregnancy	cm/week	0.2 (0.02)	5660	0.2 (0.02)	7564	0.2 (0.02)	465
Birth Outcomes							
Birth weight	grams	3207 (574)	12294	3243 (540)	8286	3275 (459)	460
HC at birth	cm	na	na	33.8 (1.7)	4406	34.2 (1.4)	454
Birth length	cm	na	na	50.2 (2.4)	5184	49.7 (2.0)	455
<hr/>							
	<i>Unit</i>	INMA – Gipuzkoa		INMA – Sabadell		INMA - Valencia	
		<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean (SD)</i>	<i>N</i>
Foetal size							
EFW at mid pregnancy	grams	406 (72)	580	397 (108)	602	348 (64)	696
EFW at late pregnancy	grams	2292 (344)	561	2405 (284)	599	1957 (300)	671
HC at mid pregnancy	cm	18.3 (1.4)	536	18.4 (2.5)	600	17.2 (1.3)	662
HC at late pregnancy	cm	30.2 (1.5)	497	31.0 (1.2)	600	29.0 (1.4)	637
FL at mid pregnancy	cm	3.5 (0.4)	583	3.4 (0.6)	605	3.2 (0.3)	696
FL at late pregnancy	cm	6.5 (0.4)	569	6.6 (0.3)	602	6.1 (0.3)	671
Foetal growth							
EFW growth from mid to late pregnancy	grams/week	146.2 (19.9)	547	151.7 (18.4)	591	134.8 (19.1)	660
HC growth from mid to late pregnancy	cm/week	0.9 (0.1)	451	0.9 (0.1)	590	1.0 (0.1)	594
FL growth from mid to late pregnancy	cm/week	0.2 (0.02)	557	0.2 (0.02)	597	0.2 (0.02)	660
Birth Outcomes							
Birth weight	grams	3301 (448)	593	3246 (425)	608	3255 (488)	709
HC at birth	cm	34.8 (1.4)	559	34.2 (1.2)	596	34.1 (1.5)	707
Birth length	cm	49.0 (1.9)	557	49.4 (1.9)	595	50.2 (2.1)	708

Abbreviations: EFW, estimated foetal weight; FL, femur length; HC, head circumference; na, not available. Values are in mean (standard deviation).

Table S8. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and foetal size metrics in standard deviation scores in the three European birth cohorts.

Temperature (°C)	Foetal size at mid pregnancy									Foetal size at late pregnancy								
	Estimated foetal weight (N = 17,972)			Head circumference (N = 20,912)			Femur length (N = 20,988)			Estimated foetal weight (N = 15,261)			Head circumference (N = 15,263)			Femur length (N = 15,785)		
	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
3.5	0.10	-1.17	1.38	-0.12	-0.71	0.46	-0.08	-0.30	0.14	0.11	-0.30	0.53	-1.22	-2.96	0.52	-0.84	-1.55	-0.13
4	0.06	-1.04	1.16	-0.12	-0.65	0.42	-0.04	-0.26	0.18	0.09	-0.31	0.50	-1.34	-3.01	0.32	-0.82	-1.50	-0.15
4.5	0.02	-0.94	0.98	-0.11	-0.60	0.38	0.00	-0.22	0.22	0.07	-0.32	0.47	-1.46	-3.07	0.15	-0.81	-1.45	-0.16
5	-0.01	-0.88	0.85	-0.11	-0.56	0.34	0.04	-0.19	0.26	0.06	-0.34	0.45	-1.56	-3.12	0.01	-0.79	-1.40	-0.17
5.5	-0.05	-0.85	0.76	-0.10	-0.52	0.31	0.07	-0.17	0.30	0.04	-0.36	0.44	-1.64	-3.17	-0.12	-0.77	-1.36	-0.17
6	-0.08	-0.87	0.71	-0.10	-0.48	0.28	0.10	-0.14	0.34	0.02	-0.37	0.42	-1.71	-3.21	-0.21	-0.74	-1.31	-0.17
6.5	-0.10	-0.91	0.70	-0.09	-0.45	0.26	0.13	-0.12	0.38	0.01	-0.39	0.41	-1.76	-3.23	-0.29	-0.71	-1.27	-0.16
7	-0.12	-0.97	0.72	-0.09	-0.42	0.24	0.15	-0.10	0.40	0.00	-0.41	0.40	-1.79	-3.24	-0.35	-0.69	-1.22	-0.15
7.5	-0.14	-1.02	0.74	-0.08	-0.40	0.23	0.17	-0.09	0.42	-0.01	-0.42	0.39	-1.80	-3.22	-0.39	-0.65	-1.17	-0.14
8	-0.15	-1.07	0.76	-0.08	-0.37	0.21	0.18	-0.07	0.44	-0.02	-0.42	0.37	-1.79	-3.17	-0.42	-0.62	-1.11	-0.12
8.5	-0.16	-1.10	0.78	-0.07	-0.35	0.20	0.19	-0.06	0.44	-0.03	-0.42	0.36	-1.76	-3.09	-0.43	-0.58	-1.05	-0.10
9	-0.17	-1.11	0.78	-0.07	-0.33	0.19	0.19	-0.05	0.44	-0.04	-0.41	0.34	-1.70	-2.97	-0.43	-0.53	-0.98	-0.08
9.5	-0.16	-1.09	0.77	-0.07	-0.31	0.18	0.19	-0.04	0.43	-0.04	-0.40	0.32	-1.61*	-2.81*	-0.42*	-0.49	-0.91	-0.07
10	-0.15	-1.04	0.73	-0.06	-0.28	0.16	0.19	-0.03	0.40	-0.04	-0.38	0.29	-1.50*	-2.60*	-0.40*	-0.44	-0.82	-0.05
10.5	-0.14	-0.97	0.69	-0.06	-0.26	0.14	0.17	-0.03	0.37	-0.04	-0.35	0.26	-1.36*	-2.36*	-0.37*	-0.39	-0.73	-0.04
11	-0.13	-0.87	0.62	-0.05	-0.23	0.12	0.16	-0.02	0.33	-0.04	-0.31	0.23	-1.21*	-2.08*	-0.33*	-0.33	-0.63	-0.03
11.5	-0.11	-0.76	0.54	-0.05	-0.20	0.10	0.14	-0.01	0.29	-0.04	-0.27	0.19	-1.03*	-1.78*	-0.29*	-0.27	-0.53	-0.02
12	-0.09	-0.62	0.45	-0.04	-0.16	0.08	0.11	-0.01	0.24	-0.03	-0.22	0.16	-0.84*	-1.45*	-0.24*	-0.22	-0.43	-0.01
12.5	-0.06	-0.48	0.35	-0.03	-0.12	0.06	0.09	-0.01	0.18	-0.03	-0.17	0.12	-0.64*	-1.10*	-0.18*	-0.16	-0.32	-0.00
13	-0.04	-0.32	0.24	-0.02	-0.08	0.04	0.06	-0.00	0.12	-0.02	-0.12	0.08	-0.43*	-0.74*	-0.13*	-0.10	-0.21	0.00
13.5	-0.02	-0.16	0.12	-0.01	-0.04	0.02	0.03	-0.00	0.06	-0.01	-0.06	0.04	-0.22*	-0.37*	-0.06*	-0.05	-0.10	0.00
14	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (mid pregnancy) or 1 to 28 (late pregnancy) of pregnancy. Global estimates and 95% confidence intervals were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (14 °C). Bold values indicate associations that are significant at the 0.05 level and an asterisk (*) indicates associations that survived multiple testing correction (p-value < 0.0083). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: Coef., coefficient; CI, confidence interval; Ref, reference.

Table S8, continued. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and foetal size metrics in standard deviation scores in the three European birth cohorts.

Temperature (°C)	Foetal size at mid pregnancy									Foetal size at late pregnancy								
	Estimated foetal weight (N = 17,972)			Head circumference (N = 20,912)			Femur length (N = 20,988)			Estimated foetal weight (N = 15,261)			Head circumference (N = 15,263)			Femur length (N = 15,785)		
	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
14	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
14.5	0.02	-0.13	0.16	0.01	-0.02	0.04	-0.03	-0.06	0.00	0.01	-0.04	0.06	0.22*	0.07*	0.37*	0.05	0.00	0.10
15	0.03	-0.25	0.32	0.03	-0.03	0.09	-0.06	-0.12	0.00	0.02	-0.08	0.12	0.43*	0.14*	0.73*	0.09	-0.01	0.19
15.5	0.04	-0.38	0.46	0.05	-0.04	0.14	-0.09	-0.18	0.00	0.03	-0.12	0.18	0.64*	0.21*	1.08*	0.13	-0.02	0.28
16	0.05	-0.50	0.60	0.07	-0.05	0.19	-0.12	-0.24	-0.00	0.04	-0.15	0.24	0.84*	0.28*	1.41*	0.16	-0.03	0.35
16.5	0.05	-0.62	0.71	0.09	-0.06	0.24	-0.15	-0.29	-0.00	0.06	-0.18	0.30	1.03*	0.35*	1.72*	0.19	-0.05	0.42
17	0.04	-0.73	0.81	0.12	-0.06	0.29	-0.17	-0.34	-0.00	0.07	-0.21	0.35	1.21*	0.41*	2.00*	0.20	-0.07	0.47
17.5	0.03	-0.83	0.89	0.14	-0.05	0.34	-0.19	-0.38	-0.00	0.08	-0.24	0.40	1.36*	0.48*	2.24*	0.21	-0.09	0.51
18	0.00	-0.93	0.94	0.18	-0.04	0.39	-0.21	-0.41	-0.01	0.09	-0.27	0.44	1.50*	0.54*	2.46*	0.21	-0.11	0.54
18.5	-0.03	-1.01	0.96	0.21	-0.02	0.45	-0.22	-0.44	-0.01	0.10	-0.29	0.48	1.61*	0.59*	2.63*	0.20	-0.14	0.55
19	-0.07	-1.09	0.95	0.25	-0.00	0.50	-0.23	-0.46	-0.01	0.11	-0.30	0.52	1.70*	0.63*	2.76*	0.18	-0.18	0.54
19.5	-0.12	-1.16	0.91	0.29	0.02	0.56	-0.24	-0.46	-0.01	0.12	-0.31	0.55	1.75*	0.66*	2.85*	0.15	-0.22	0.52
20	-0.18	-1.22	0.85	0.34	0.05	0.63	-0.23	-0.46	-0.01	0.13	-0.32	0.57	1.78*	0.66*	2.90*	0.11	-0.28	0.49
20.5	-0.26	-1.29	0.77	0.39	0.07	0.70	-0.23	-0.45	-0.00	0.14	-0.32	0.59	1.78*	0.64*	2.93*	0.05	-0.34	0.45
21	-0.34	-1.36	0.69	0.44	0.10	0.78	-0.22	-0.44	0.00	0.14	-0.33	0.61	1.76*	0.57*	2.95*	-0.01	-0.42	0.41
21.5	-0.43	-1.46	0.60	0.49	0.12	0.87	-0.20	-0.42	0.01	0.15	-0.33	0.63	1.71*	0.47*	2.96*	-0.08	-0.52	0.36
22	-0.52	-1.58	0.53	0.55	0.14	0.96	-0.19	-0.41	0.03	0.16	-0.33	0.64	1.65	0.32	2.97	-0.16	-0.64	0.32
22.5	-0.63	-1.74	0.48	0.61	0.15	1.07	-0.17	-0.39	0.06	0.16	-0.33	0.65	1.56	0.12	3.00	-0.25	-0.78	0.28
23	-0.74	-1.93	0.46	0.67	0.17	1.18	-0.14	-0.37	0.09	0.17	-0.34	0.67	1.46	-0.12	3.04	-0.34	-0.93	0.24
23.5	-0.85	-2.17	0.46	0.74	0.18	1.30	-0.12	-0.36	0.13	0.17	-0.34	0.69	1.34	-0.42	3.09	-0.44	-1.10	0.21
24	-0.97	-2.44	0.49	0.80	0.18	1.42	-0.09	-0.35	0.18	0.17	-0.36	0.70	1.20	-0.75	3.16	-0.55	-1.28	0.18
24.5	-1.09	-2.74	0.55	0.87	0.19	1.55	-0.06	-0.35	0.24	0.18	-0.37	0.73	1.06	-1.12	3.24	-0.66	-1.48	0.16

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (mid pregnancy) or 1 to 28 (late pregnancy) of pregnancy. Global estimates and 95% confidence intervals were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (14 °C). Bold values indicate associations that are significant at the 0.05 level and an asterisk (*) indicates associations that survived multiple testing correction (p-value < 0.0083). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: Coef., coefficient; CI, confidence interval; Ref, reference.

Table S9. Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure at the 2.5th or 97.5th percentile during each week of pregnancy and head circumference SDS at late pregnancy (N = 15,263).

Pregnancy week (lag)	<i>Exposure to 2.5th percentile (4.2 °C)</i>			<i>Exposure to 97.5th percentile (23.9 °C)</i>		
	Coefficient	95% Confidence Interval		Coefficient	95% Confidence Interval	
1	-0.19	-0.37	-0.00	0.12	-0.07	0.30
2	-0.17	-0.34	-0.01	0.10	-0.07	0.26
3	-0.16	-0.30	-0.01	0.08	-0.07	0.22
4	-0.14	-0.27	-0.01	0.06	-0.07	0.19
5	-0.13	-0.24	-0.01	0.04	-0.07	0.16
6	-0.11	-0.22	-0.01	0.03	-0.07	0.13
7	-0.10	-0.19	-0.00	0.01	-0.08	0.10
8	-0.09	-0.17	0.00	0.00	-0.08	0.08
9	-0.07	-0.16	0.01	-0.01	-0.09	0.06
10	-0.06	-0.14	0.02	-0.03	-0.10	0.05
11	-0.05	-0.13	0.03	-0.03	-0.11	0.04
12	-0.04	-0.12	0.04	-0.04	-0.12	0.04
13	-0.03	-0.11	0.05	-0.04	-0.12	0.03
14	-0.03	-0.10	0.05	-0.05	-0.13	0.03
15	-0.02	-0.09	0.06	-0.05	-0.12	0.03
16	-0.01	-0.09	0.06	-0.04	-0.12	0.03
17	-0.01	-0.08	0.06	-0.04	-0.11	0.04
18	-0.01	-0.07	0.06	-0.03	-0.09	0.04
19	0.00	-0.07	0.06	-0.02	-0.08	0.05
20	0.00	-0.06	0.06	0.00	-0.07	0.06
21	0.00	-0.06	0.06	0.01	-0.05	0.07
22	0.00	-0.07	0.06	0.03	-0.04	0.09
23	0.00	-0.08	0.07	0.04	-0.03	0.12
24	0.00	-0.09	0.08	0.06	-0.03	0.15
25	-0.01	-0.11	0.09	0.08	-0.02	0.18
26	-0.01	-0.12	0.11	0.10	-0.02	0.22
27	-0.01	-0.14	0.12	0.12	-0.02	0.25
28	-0.01	-0.16	0.13	0.14	-0.01	0.29

Global estimates and 95% confidence intervals were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (14 °C). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education level, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviation: SDS, standard deviation score. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles correspond to the average temperature in all cohorts/regions during weeks 1 to 28 of pregnancy.

Table S10. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and foetal growth metrics from mid to late pregnancy in the three European birth cohorts.

Temperature (°C)	Estimated foetal weight (g/week) (N = 13,184)			Head circumference (cm/week) (N = 14,707)			Femur length (cm/week) (N = 15,312)		
	Coefficient	95% CI		Coefficient	95% CI		Coefficient	95% CI	
3.5	-9.78	-17.45	-2.10	-0.16	-0.32	0.01	-0.03	-0.05	-0.00
4.0	-8.98	-16.29	-1.67	-0.15	-0.29	-0.01	-0.03	-0.05	-0.00
4.5	-8.21	-15.20	-1.22	-0.14	-0.26	-0.02	-0.02	-0.04	-0.00
5.0	-7.46	-14.18	-0.75	-0.13	-0.23	-0.03	-0.02	-0.04	-0.00
5.5	-6.74	-13.21	-0.26	-0.13*	-0.21*	-0.04*	-0.02	-0.04	0.00
6.0	-6.04	-12.30	0.22	-0.12*	-0.20*	-0.04*	-0.02	-0.04	0.00
6.5	-5.37	-11.44	0.69	-0.11*	-0.18*	-0.04*	-0.01	-0.03	0.01
7.0	-4.74	-10.61	1.13	-0.10*	-0.18*	-0.03*	-0.01	-0.03	0.01
7.5	-4.14	-9.81	1.53	-0.09	-0.17	-0.02	-0.01	-0.03	0.01
8.0	-3.58	-9.03	1.87	-0.09	-0.17	-0.00	-0.01	-0.03	0.02
8.5	-3.06	-8.26	2.15	-0.08	-0.16	0.01	-0.01	-0.03	0.02
9.0	-2.57	-7.49	2.34	-0.07	-0.16	0.02	0.00	-0.03	0.02
9.5	-2.14	-6.72	2.44	-0.06	-0.15	0.02	0.00	-0.03	0.02
10.0	-1.75	-5.94	2.45	-0.06	-0.14	0.03	0.00	-0.02	0.02
10.5	-1.40	-5.15	2.36	-0.05	-0.13	0.03	0.00	-0.02	0.02
11.0	-1.09	-4.36	2.18	-0.04	-0.11	0.03	0.00	-0.02	0.02
11.5	-0.82	-3.58	1.94	-0.03	-0.09	0.03	0.00	-0.02	0.02
12.0	-0.59	-2.81	1.63	-0.03	-0.08	0.02	0.00	-0.01	0.01
12.5	-0.39	-2.06	1.27	-0.02	-0.06	0.02	0.00	-0.01	0.01
13.0	-0.23	-1.34	0.87	-0.01	-0.04	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.01
13.5	-0.10	-0.65	0.44	-0.01	-0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
14.0	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
14.5	0.07	-0.45	0.60	0.01	-0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
15.0	0.12	-0.90	1.14	0.01	-0.01	0.04	0.00	-0.01	0.01
15.5	0.14	-1.33	1.61	0.02	-0.02	0.05	0.00	-0.01	0.01
16.0	0.15	-1.73	2.02	0.02	-0.03	0.07	0.00	-0.01	0.01
16.5	0.13	-2.10	2.36	0.03	-0.03	0.08	0.00	-0.01	0.02
17.0	0.09	-2.43	2.61	0.03	-0.03	0.09	0.00	-0.01	0.02
17.5	0.04	-2.72	2.80	0.03	-0.04	0.10	0.00	-0.01	0.02
18.0	-0.03	-2.97	2.91	0.04	-0.04	0.11	0.01	-0.01	0.02
18.5	-0.11	-3.18	2.97	0.04	-0.04	0.11	0.01	-0.01	0.03
19.0	-0.20	-3.38	2.99	0.04	-0.04	0.11	0.01	-0.01	0.03
19.5	-0.30	-3.61	3.01	0.04	-0.03	0.12	0.01	-0.01	0.03
20.0	-0.40	-3.90	3.09	0.04	-0.03	0.12	0.01	-0.00	0.03
20.5	-0.52	-4.33	3.29	0.04	-0.04	0.12	0.02	-0.00	0.03
21.0	-0.64	-4.91	3.63	0.04	-0.05	0.13	0.02	0.00	0.04
21.5	-0.77	-5.67	4.13	0.04	-0.06	0.14	0.02	0.00	0.04
22.0	-0.90	-6.59	4.78	0.04	-0.09	0.16	0.03	0.00	0.05
22.5	-1.04	-7.65	5.57	0.04	-0.11	0.19	0.03	0.00	0.06
23.0	-1.18	-8.85	6.48	0.04	-0.14	0.21	0.03	0.00	0.07
23.5	-1.33	-10.16	7.49	0.03	-0.18	0.24	0.04	0.00	0.08
24.0	-1.48	-11.56	8.59	0.03	-0.21	0.27	0.04	-0.00	0.09
24.5	-1.64	-13.03	9.76	0.03	-0.25	0.30	0.05	-0.00	0.10

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 of pregnancy. Global estimates and 95% confidence intervals were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (14 °C). Bold values indicate associations that are significant at the 0.05 level and an asterisk (*) indicates associations that survived multiple testing correction (p-value < 0.0083). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for foetal sex, maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; Ref, reference.

Table S11. Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure at the 2.5th percentile (4.2 °C) during each week of pregnancy and head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy in centimetres per week (N = 14,707).

Pregnancy week (lag)	Coefficient	95% Confidence Interval	
1	-0.01	-0.03	0.01
2	-0.01	-0.02	0.01
3	-0.01	-0.02	0.00
4	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
5	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
6	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
7	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
8	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
9	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
10	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
11	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
12	-0.01	-0.02	-0.00
13	-0.01	-0.02	0.00
14	-0.01	-0.02	0.01
15	-0.01	-0.02	0.01
16	0.00	-0.02	0.02
17	0.00	-0.03	0.02
18	0.00	-0.03	0.03

Global estimates and 95% confidence intervals were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (14 °C). Bolded values indicate significance at the 0.05 level. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for foetal sex, maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education level, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception.

Table S12. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure at various °C during pregnancy and birth outcomes standard deviation scores in two* or three European birth cohorts.**

Temperature (°C)	Birth weight** (N = 22,950)			Head circumference at birth* (N = 6,722)			Birth length* (N = 7,499)		
	Coefficient	95% CI		Coefficient	95% CI		Coefficient	95% CI	
3.5	0.19	-0.17	0.56						
4	0.16	-0.17	0.49	0.54	-0.32	1.40	-0.29	-2.16	1.58
4.5	0.13	-0.17	0.43	0.45	-0.35	1.25	-0.25	-1.90	1.40
5	0.10	-0.17	0.37	0.36	-0.37	1.10	-0.21	-1.65	1.23
5.5	0.07	-0.18	0.32	0.28	-0.40	0.96	-0.17	-1.42	1.08
6	0.04	-0.19	0.27	0.20	-0.43	0.83	-0.14	-1.20	0.93
6.5	0.02	-0.20	0.23	0.13	-0.46	0.72	-0.10	-1.01	0.80
7	0.00	-0.21	0.20	0.06	-0.50	0.62	-0.07	-0.84	0.69
7.5	-0.02	-0.22	0.17	0.00	-0.53	0.53	-0.04	-0.69	0.60
8	-0.04	-0.23	0.15	-0.05	-0.55	0.45	-0.02	-0.57	0.54
8.5	-0.05	-0.24	0.13	-0.10	-0.58	0.38	0.01	-0.48	0.50
9	-0.06	-0.24	0.12	-0.13	-0.59	0.33	0.03	-0.43	0.48
9.5	-0.07	-0.24	0.10	-0.16	-0.60	0.28	0.04	-0.39	0.48
10	-0.07	-0.23	0.09	-0.18	-0.60	0.23	0.06	-0.37	0.49
10.5	-0.07	-0.21	0.08	-0.19	-0.58	0.20	0.07	-0.36	0.49
11	-0.07	-0.20	0.06	-0.19	-0.55	0.17	0.07	-0.34	0.49
11.5	-0.06	-0.17	0.05	-0.19	-0.51	0.14	0.07	-0.32	0.47
12	-0.05	-0.14	0.04	-0.17	-0.46	0.11	0.07	-0.29	0.44
12.5	-0.04	-0.11	0.03	-0.15	-0.40	0.09	0.07	-0.26	0.39
13	-0.03	-0.08	0.02	-0.13	-0.33	0.07	0.06	-0.21	0.34
13.5	-0.02	-0.04	0.01	-0.10	-0.25	0.05	0.05	-0.17	0.27
14	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	-0.07	-0.17	0.03	0.04	-0.11	0.19
14.5	0.02	-0.01	0.04	-0.03	-0.09	0.02	0.02	-0.06	0.10
15	0.03	-0.02	0.08	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
15.5	0.05	-0.02	0.12	0.03	-0.02	0.09	-0.02	-0.10	0.06
16	0.07	-0.03	0.16	0.07	-0.03	0.17	-0.05	-0.21	0.11
16.5	0.08	-0.03	0.20	0.10	-0.05	0.25	-0.08	-0.32	0.17
17	0.10	-0.04	0.24	0.13	-0.07	0.32	-0.11	-0.43	0.22
17.5	0.12	-0.04	0.28	0.15	-0.09	0.39	-0.14	-0.54	0.26
18	0.13	-0.05	0.31	0.17	-0.12	0.45	-0.17	-0.65	0.30
18.5	0.15	-0.05	0.34	0.18	-0.14	0.50	-0.21	-0.75	0.33
19	0.16	-0.05	0.37	0.19	-0.17	0.54	-0.25	-0.85	0.35
19.5	0.17	-0.06	0.40	0.18	-0.21	0.57	-0.29	-0.94	0.36
20	0.18	-0.07	0.43	0.17	-0.24	0.58	-0.33	-1.03	0.36
20.5	0.19	-0.08	0.45	0.15	-0.29	0.58	-0.38	-1.10	0.34
21	0.19	-0.09	0.48	0.11	-0.34	0.57	-0.43	-1.17	0.32
21.5	0.20	-0.11	0.50	0.07	-0.41	0.55	-0.47	-1.22	0.28
22	0.20	-0.13	0.53	0.02	-0.48	0.52	-0.52	-1.28	0.23
22.5	0.20	-0.16	0.57	-0.04	-0.56	0.48	-0.57	-1.33	0.18
23	0.20	-0.20	0.60	-0.11	-0.66	0.45	-0.63	-1.38	0.13
23.5	0.20	-0.23	0.64	-0.18	-0.78	0.41	-0.68	-1.43	0.07
24	0.20	-0.28	0.68	-0.26	-0.90	0.37	-0.73	-1.49	0.03
24.5	0.20	-0.32	0.72	-0.35	-1.04	0.34	-0.79	-1.56	-0.02
25				-0.44	-1.19	0.31	-0.85	-1.64	-0.05
25.5				-0.54	-1.35	0.28	-0.90	-1.73	-0.07
26				-0.64	-1.53	0.25	-0.96	-1.84	-0.08

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 32 of pregnancy. Global estimates and 95% confidence interval were obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (14 or 15 °C). Bold values indicate associations that are significant at the 0.05 level. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for parental age, education level, national origin, and body mass index, maternal smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, folic acid use periconceptionally, parity, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval;

Ref, reference. * The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length.

Figure S5. Adjusted associations between ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and (top) head circumference at birth (N = 6,722) and (bottom) birth length (N = 7,499) in the two European birth cohorts.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in these analyses. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 32 of pregnancy. The continuous red line represents the population-average curve the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. All estimates are centred at the 50th percentile (15 °C). Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for parental age, education level, national origin, and body mass index, maternal smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, folic acid use periconceptionally, parity, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S6. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, with knots placed at the 10th and 90th percentile temperature distribution in the exposure-response relationship.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 32 (D) weeks pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S7. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, with the lag-response relationship modelled linearly.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 32 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S8. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, with with two equally distributed knots in the lag-response relationship

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 32 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S9. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts only including mothers with available temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 38 of pregnancy

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 38 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S10. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and birth weight, head circumference at birth, and birth length in the three European birth cohorts, using a lag period of 18- or 28-weeks during pregnancy.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (14 °C for birth weight and 15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted.

Figure S11. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, stratified by foetal sex.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 38 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S11, continued. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, stratified by foetal sex.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 38 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S12. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in the three European birth cohorts, only for mothers who had a national origin of the respective cohort.

The Born in Bradford cohort was not included in the analyses for head circumference at birth or birth length. Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 38 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C for head circumference at birth and birth length analyses and 14 °C for all other outcomes). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S13. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and head circumference at late pregnancy in each cohort/region of the three European birth cohorts.

Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution during pregnancy weeks 1 to 18 (9.4, 11.6, 15.4, 14.8, 17.3, and 17.1 °C in Born in Bradford, Generation R, INMA-Asturias, -Gipuzkoa, -Sabadell, and -Valencia, respectively). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from distributed lag non-linear models. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted.

Figure S14. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and head circumference growth from mid to late pregnancy in each cohort/region of the three European birth cohorts.

Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution during pregnancy weeks 1 to 28 (9.2, 11.3, 14.9, 15.6, 17.4, and 15.7 °C in Born in Bradford, Generation R, INMA-Asturias, -Gipuzkoa, -Sabadell, and -Valencia, respectively). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from distributed lag non-linear models. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for foetal sex, maternal age, education level, national origin, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted.

Figure S15. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C), and birth outcomes (D) in two European birth cohorts (Born in Bradford not included).

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C), 28 (B), or 32 (D) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (15 °C). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Models evaluating foetal growth outcomes were additionally adjusted for foetal sex. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

Figure S16. Adjusted associations between cumulative ambient air temperature exposure (°C) during pregnancy and foetal size at mid (A) and late (B) pregnancy, foetal growth from mid to late pregnancy (C) in the three European birth cohorts, only for mothers who had available data at both the mid and late pregnancy assessments.

Ambient air temperature exposure during weeks 1 to 18 (A and C) or 28 (B) weeks of pregnancy. Estimates are centred at the 50th percentile of temperature distribution (14 °C). The continuous red line represents the population-average curve with the 95% confidence intervals shaded in grey obtained from random-effects meta-analysis. Within each cohort/region, distributed lag non-linear models were adjusted for maternal age, education level, body mass index, smoking and alcohol use during pregnancy, parity, paternal education, family status, surrounding greenness and month of conception. Standard deviation scores are gestational age- and sex-adjusted. Abbreviations: SDS, standard deviation score.

References

- Annoni, A., Luzet, C., Gubler, E., & Ihde, J. (2001). *Map Projections for Europe*.
- Copernicus. (n.d.). *Land Imperviousness*. Retrieved November 29, 2022, from <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/imperviousness>
- Copernicus. (n.d.). *CORINE Land Cover*. Retrieved November 29, 2022, from <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>
- De Ridder, K., Lauwaet, D., & Maiheu, B. (2015). UrbClim - A fast urban boundary layer climate model. *Urban Climate*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2015.01.001>
- ECMWF. (n.d.). *ERA5*. Retrieved November 29, 2022, from <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5>
- García-Diéz, M., Lauwaet, D., Hooyberghs, H., Ballester, J., de Ridder, K., & Rodó, X. (2016). Advantages of using a fast urban boundary layer model as compared to a full mesoscale model to simulate the urban heat island of Barcelona. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(12). <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-9-4439-2016>
- Golan, R., Kloog, I., Almog, R., Gesser-Edelsburg, A., Negev, M., Jolles, M., Shalev, V., Eisenberg, V. H., Koren, G., Abu Ahmad, W., & Levine, H. (2018). Environmental exposures and fetal growth: the Haifa pregnancy cohort study. *BMC Public Health*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5030-8>
- Honaker, J., King, G., & Blackwell, M. (2012). *AMELIA II: A Program for Missing Data, Version 1.6.2*.
- Lauwaet, D., de Ridder, K., Saeed, S., Brisson, E., Chatterjee, F., van Lipzig, N. P. M., Maiheu, B., & Hooyberghs, H. (2016). Assessing the current and future urban heat island of Brussels. *Urban Climate*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2015.11.008>
- Lauwaet, D., Hooyberghs, H., Maiheu, B., Lefebvre, W., Driesen, G., van Looy, S., & de Ridder, K. (2015). Detailed urban heat island projections for cities worldwide: Dynamical downscaling CMIP5 global climate models. *Climate*, 3(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli3020391>
- NASA. (n.d.). *MODIS Vegetation Index Products (NDVI and EVI)*. Retrieved November 29, 2022, from <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/dataproduct/mod13.php>
- SOISE. (n.d.). *SOISE Land Cover*. Retrieved November 29, 2022, from <https://www.siose.es/presentacion>